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The two roles of Ca²⁺ signaling

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Abstract

Genes are the determinants and limiting constraints of all the possible features a living organism can display. Genes, however, are largely lineage-specific, and a strict focus on them can lead to an overlook of functional analogies existing between organisms belonging to non-related lineages. In the present concept work we propose that: 1) Ca²⁺ signaling is a general, cross-kingdom, regulatory pathway encompassing lineage-specific gene-defined morphogenesis in multicellular organisms, 2) to understand its way of action, Ca²⁺ signaling should be approached from the viewpoint of the functional blocks involved in the execution of migration, proliferation and other cellular-level processes. Two major roles are attributed to Ca²⁺ signaling within this framework: the “classical”, stimulus-transducing *triggering* role, and a second one, here termed *orchestrating*, reflecting the responsive regulation of Ca²⁺ signaling properties by Ca²⁺ signaling itself. Approaching Ca²⁺ signaling from this perspective reveals currently hard-to-formalize general structural features of living organisms, experimental validation of which would otherwise require an extremely large number of “wet” analyses, and to which bioinformatics methods alone can be blind.

Keywords

Ca²⁺ signaling, proliferation, chemotaxis, differentiation, morphogenesis, development, regeneration, cancer, bauplan, organism

Glossary

A glossary to the terms and concepts used in the present work is available at the Supplementary Note.

Content

1. Introduction	3
2. The “orchestrating” role of Ca ²⁺ signals.....	4
2.1 Background Ca ²⁺ level.....	5
2.2 Ca ²⁺ signaling in the migration-chemotaxis functional block	9
2.2.1. <i>Cell migration types and transitions between them</i>	9
2.2.2. <i>Ca²⁺ signaling structure responsible for cell traction and fine tuning of migration direction</i>	11
2.3 The role of Ca ²⁺ signaling in the proliferation-quiescence-based functional block ...	20
2.3.1. <i>Stemness</i>	21
2.3.2. <i>Proliferation</i>	23
2.3.3. <i>Quiescence</i>	25
2.3.4. <i>Apoptosis</i>	27
2.3.5. <i>Differentiation</i>	29
2.4 Ca ²⁺ signaling in the multicellular environment.....	31
2.4.1. <i>Cell-cell interaction (differentiating/specificating) means</i>	33
2.4.2. <i>Interaction of differentiating/specificating means and Ca²⁺ signaling during development. Establishment of specific Ca²⁺ signaling toolkit configurations</i>	44
2.4.3. <i>Cancer</i>	51
2.4.4. <i>Regeneration</i>	55
3. The “triggering” role of Ca ²⁺ signals.....	58
4. Orchestrating-to-triggering role transition and orchestrating-triggering coupling.....	59
5. Ca ²⁺ signaling flexibility and robustness.....	60
Conclusions	62

1. Introduction

Ca²⁺ transients are routinely recorded in biological experiments as *par excellence* indicators that “something is happening” to the monitored sample, as a “marker of activity”, and a passive response of the biological system to stimuli. Ca²⁺ ion is accepted in its role of a universal messenger, transducing numerous Ca²⁺ transients-evoking stimuli into no-less multiple physiological responses it mediates (the so called “bow tie scheme”, Berridge et al., 2000; Dodd et al., 2010; Brodskiy and Zartman, 2018).

Ca²⁺ signaling has become familiar to biologists to the extent that some of its basic features are rarely questioned. Typically, it is approached from the perspective of Ca²⁺ sources and transporters involved in this ion’s translocation. For instance, particular composition of the “Ca²⁺ signaling toolkit” (Berridge et al., 2000) in organisms belonging to different taxa has been in the focus of numerous studies (Marchadier et al., 2016; Edel et al., 2017; Plattner and Verkhatsky, 2018). Another approach focuses on the participation of Ca²⁺ signaling in specific processes (diseases, tissular physiology, etc.). Up to now, the “Ca²⁺ response” paradigm has kept in shade other possible roles of Ca²⁺ signaling (Chan et al., 2017), although evidence exists against such a simplistic view, suggesting the existence of categories and layers of Ca²⁺ signaling. Similar Ca²⁺ responses can be observed in very different systems, experiencing similar changes: tip-focused Ca²⁺ gradients in growing pollen tubes resemble those in growing axons, fertilization-induced waves in animals mimic those observed in plants, suggesting the possibility that such processes are governed by structurally similar regulatory mechanisms (Rudd and Franklin-Tong, 2001). A single Ca²⁺ increase could activate all Ca²⁺-dependent processes (acting as a “consensus signal”; Brodskiy and Zartman, 2018), but certain genes and proteins require Ca²⁺ transients of specific frequencies for their activation (Aguilera et al., 2019), raising the question of the nature of the differences between the processes that demand such particular modes of activation, or in which Ca²⁺ transients serve as discriminators (leading to “mutually exclusive behaviors”; Brodskiy and Zartman, 2018).

In the present work we propose a different approach to Ca²⁺ signaling. We select common Ca²⁺-dependent cellular processes —hereinafter called *programs*— that appear essential for the emergence of multicellular organisms and their morphogenesis. Programs are then grouped into *functional blocks*. A particular *program* comprises a group of functionally linked Ca²⁺ transporters of different types, involved in its execution. We, nevertheless, assume that a specific transporter type can belong to more than one group, and can thus be involved in the execution of more than one program (Fig 1).

We propose the existence of two major relatively independent and mutually exclusive functional blocks, which are essential for development. The first block consists of the migration and chemotaxis programs, found mostly in metazoans, whereas the second block is based on proliferation and quiescence, but includes also apoptosis and differentiation, being these last four programs common for all multicellular eukaryotic organisms. The

proposed mutual exclusivity of the blocks is based on the assumption that the participation of Ca^{2+} -handling proteins in tasks from the first block reduces the possibility of their participation in tasks from the second functional block. This mutual exclusivity, however, has a statistical character, as the number of involved Ca^{2+} -handling proteins of any kind can be large, even within a same cell.

Abstraction from non-homologous lineages-specific details allowed us to compare the general structural and functional organization of the mechanisms regulating the abovementioned programs at the cellular and supracellular levels. From this analysis, we propose that Ca^{2+} is a general mediator of morphogenesis and morphology dynamics in multicellular organisms, but the mechanisms of its action differs amongst major lineages.

2. The “orchestrating” role of Ca^{2+} signals

The notion that some factors can play an orchestrating (*arranging*) role in physiological processes at different levels emerged at the end of the XXth century. According to this notion, such factors represent hubs on which different kinds of inputs converge, and which, on the other hand, control a wide range of downstream physiological processes.

Among such factors, Ca^{2+} has a particular place, as one of its central features is its rapid removal upon intracellular increase (Berridge et al., 2000; Brunet and Arendt, 2015), at a first glance impinging on this ion’s ability to mediate long-term processes with which orchestration should be associated. Nevertheless, despite the short-lived nature of intracellular Ca^{2+} transients *per se*, recently an orchestrating role for them has been proposed in plants (Choi et al., 2017). This term, however, has been used rather to denote the participation of Ca^{2+} waves (together with ROS and electrical signals) in keeping different plant parts “communicated” and “aware” about the environment surrounding the other parts of the plant.

Given the central role Ca^{2+} plays in mediating different processes at the subcellular and tissular level, the question of how is specificity encoded in Ca^{2+} responses has been risen in several previous studies. Currently, “ Ca^{2+} signatures” —particular intensity and spatio-temporal features of Ca^{2+} transients— are considered to encode such specificity (Webb et al., 1996; Berridge et al., 2000; Rudd and Franklin-Tong, 2001 and references therein), although the way in which such encoding is achieved has remained elusive.

The current paradigm of Ca^{2+} signaling, thus, ends deeply buried inside the cell, not explaining how feedback loops to the macroscopic manifestations of intracellular Ca^{2+} signaling are established (Fig 2A).

Curiously, despite being Ca^{2+} signaling widely acknowledged as a key physiological regulator, the possibility that it can regulate/modulate its own spatio-temporal localization and strength has been largely overlooked. Berridge and collaborators (2000) state: “One of

the fascinating aspects of Ca^{2+} is that it plays a direct role in controlling the transcriptional events that select out the types of Ca^{2+} signalling systems that are expressed in specific cell types.” A not so explicit, but similar statement on the overlooked importance of Ca^{2+} in differentiation (=“the establishment of specific Ca^{2+} signaling systems”; Berridge et al., 2000) can be found in the work of Chan and collaborators (2017), in which this specific role of Ca^{2+} is called “instructive”. In addition, notions on Ca^{2+} signaling “rewiring”, particularly in cancer, are gaining strength (see Hoth, 2016). From these few, although surely not exhaustive examples, it can be inferred that in addition to its “immediate” role as a specific cascade messenger, Ca^{2+} plays another role — of a modulator of its own signaling strength and localization, self-(de)limiting the type and amount of Ca^{2+} signaling required for the proper functioning of particular biological systems. We designate this non-messenger, “feedback” or “fine tuning” role of Ca^{2+} signaling (in contrast to the “triggering” one, see below) *orchestrating*, *arranging*, or *instructive*, even if it is additionally mediated by agents other than Ca^{2+} itself (Fig 2B).

We can expect that both roles of Ca^{2+} signaling were subjected to different pressures during evolution, resulting in the different types of Ca^{2+} transients-related phenomena that can be observed nowadays. From this “ Ca^{2+} -centric” viewpoint, cellular-scale phenomena that are typically studied separately appear tightly interconnected because of their (co)dependence on the same Ca^{2+} transients or Ca^{2+} transporters: chemotaxis, cell migration, embryonic development/regeneration, phenomena and acclimation-adaptation-plasticity as reflections of dynamically-established phenotype. Other phenomena and features that, following this assumption, should be included in this list, are Ca^{2+} background dynamics, Ca^{2+} signal robustness (the degree of Ca^{2+} signaling tolerance to changes in the surrounding environment) and flexibility (the ability of the living system to cope with and compensate for a defective Ca^{2+} signaling).

In the following sections we approach Ca^{2+} -dependent programs from the “orchestrating role” viewpoint. It should be noted, however, that as the identification of this role within Ca^{2+} signaling-associated phenomena is in its infancy, it will have to be inferred by gathering together results from different fields.

2.1 Background Ca^{2+} level

Ca^{2+} signaling is typically thought about as a Ca^{2+} level *increase*. However, Ca^{2+} transients depend not only on the cytosolic Ca^{2+} influx, but also on the background Ca^{2+} level, which is dynamically established by the joint action of Ca^{2+} -extruding and Ca^{2+} -releasing/leaking mechanisms, and can be affected by the available cytosolic Ca^{2+} buffers (Baimbridge et al., 1992; Fierro and Llano, 1996; Berridge et al., 2000).

Background Ca^{2+} level falls in the submicromolar range, but even within this range differences can be appreciated: acutely isolated hippocampal pyramidal and cerebellar Purkinje neurons display resting Ca^{2+} levels close to 50 nM (Maravall et al., 2000;

Liljelund et al., 2000), while in culture their background Ca^{2+} level rises above 100 nM (Connor and Tseng, 1988). Moreover, different parts of a same cell (like soma and dendrites in neurons) can display different background Ca^{2+} levels in resting conditions (see Tank et al., 1988).

Among other reasons, a low level of cytosolic Ca^{2+} has been proposed to be a prerequisite to avoid the formation of insoluble precipitates with ATP (e.g., after Permyakov and Kretsinger, 2009) — an argument that, although valid at a first glance, has not been experimentally tested, and does not entirely fit with the presence of ATP in the ER lumen (Vishnu et al., 2014) — a compartment with Ca^{2+} levels much higher than those present in the cytosol. As it can be appreciated from the data that will be presented below, a low cytosolic Ca^{2+} level seems rather aimed at preventing uncontrolled proliferation, apoptosis or cell (de)differentiation.

A prolonged cytosolic calcium increase provokes cellular toxicity. Nevertheless, several studies report sustained (up to ~ 60 min) Ca^{2+} increases, observable under different biotic and abiotic stimuli. In plants, some of these stimuli include ozone application, treatment with the Pep-13 elicitor, the attack of cowpea rust fungus, fertilization (Rudd and Franklin-Tong, 2001), salt stress (Choi et al., 2014), and damaging factors (e.g., burning, Vodenev et al., 2015). In animal models, prolonged Ca^{2+} increase can also be induced under specific conditions (e.g., fertilization; Berridge et al., 2000), however Ca^{2+} level oscillations are more frequently observed, with frequencies ranging from seconds to the duration of the cell cycle. Thus, at least in plant cells, a prolonged cytosolic Ca^{2+} increase is required for certain physiological processes. Unlike vegetal cells, “normal” (non-cancerous) metazoan cells have a stricter control over the amount of Ca^{2+} entering the cytosol, even during prolonged increases. The mechanism responsible for this feature is the Store Operated Channel Entry (SOCE) (Parekh and Putney, 2005). For the sake of fairness, however, it should be noted that plants are also able to display cytosolic Ca^{2+} oscillations (which are required for guard cell closure, or for the establishment of symbiosis with nitrogen-fixing bacteria; Wheeler and Brownlee, 2008), and both in animals and plants sustained Ca^{2+} increase still falls in the sub-micromolar (physiological) range.

Although relatively low, the resting Ca^{2+} level in cells is not the lowest possible one: it has been shown that some stimuli can induce its *decrease* (e.g., Fuchs et al., 2005). For example, in cortical pyramidal neurons, the overly rapid capture of cytosolic Ca^{2+} by mitochondria leads to the reduction of Ca^{2+} below resting values, and to a reduced presynaptic neurotransmitter release (Lewis Jr et al., 2018). In addition, paraphrasing Brodskiy and Zartman (2018), no known embryonic system is able to complete gastrulation in a Ca^{2+} -free medium. Thus, certain minimal cytosolic Ca^{2+} level is required for physiological processes to occur. Moreover, proliferation is apparently promoted by *elevated* cytosolic Ca^{2+} levels, both in animal and plant cells: high cytosolic Ca^{2+} level induced by expression of CD38 (see below) in 3T3 and HeLa cells, shortens the S phase of

the cell cycle and speeds up cell doubling (Zocchi et al., 1998; Berridge et al., 2000). Similarly, application of the Ca^{2+} ionophore A23187 in the presence of elevated Ca^{2+} in the external medium (A23187+ Ca^{2+}) enhances the somatic-to-embryogenic transition (which is linked to increased cell proliferation) in calli of coffee (Akula et al., 2011) and coconut (Rivera-Solís et al., 2018). In addition, pulse application of A23187 to developing sea urchin embryos produces either numerous exogastrulae or exoguts, depending on the time of the ionophore application upon fertilization, and these effects are abolished by inhibitors of ryanodine receptors (Fujiwara and Yasumasu, 1991).

These data suggest that an elevated background Ca^{2+} may as well constitute a prerequisite for directing the differentiation pathway (linking it to the cell cycle, as shown for differentiating T cells, see Viola et al., 2005). This hypothesis is supported by the fact that cytosolic Ca^{2+} level in the slime mold *Dictyostelium discoideum* correlates with the cell fate (either prestalk or prespore) after aggregation (Saran et al., 1994). A cytosolic Ca^{2+} increase induced by application of A23187+ Ca^{2+} during *Dictyostelium* development results in a longer slug and an increased proportion of prestalk cells, with the total amount of spore cells remaining approximately the same under different intracellular Ca^{2+} conditions (Baskar et al., 2000). In plants, mutation of the plasma membrane Autoinhibited Ca^{2+} -ATPases (ACA) or the tonoplast-residing Cation Exchangers (CAX) —both them Ca^{2+} -extruding mechanisms— leads to developmental defects (Dodd et al., 2010). Thus, in differentiation, the background Ca^{2+} level can be a regulating factor that can induce deviation of the cellular developmental program from the genetically predefined one. Interestingly, this role seemingly extends further to organism development and chemotaxis: in *Dictyostelium*, differential cell migration within the slug, and tip formation (“differentiation”), correlates with the cytosolic Ca^{2+} level (Cubbit et al., 1995). In more complex animals, a larger number of possible differentiation pathways (and associated stimuli-triggered cellular migration) results probably from a higher diversity of receptors and corresponding chemotactants, compared to *Dictyostelium* (e.g., see Artemenko et al., 2014).

Thus, while an elevated background Ca^{2+} level apparently promotes mitosis and some differentiation programs, its low level can be associated with (chemotaxis-driven?) cellular migration. A possible evidence of this could be the extremely low cytosolic Ca^{2+} levels in starving *Dictyostelium* cells during their aggregation. In starving and aggregating cells, visualization of cAMP-induced Ca^{2+} transients was made possible only after the development of an ultrasensitive Ca^{2+} indicator variant (YC-Nano15, $K_d = 15$ nM, Horikawa et al., 2010). In addition, no cell division has been reported for *Dictyostelium* in these conditions. It should be noted that, although in this organism Ca^{2+} measurements have been conducted using several Ca^{2+} indicators with different affinities, cytosolic Ca^{2+} level changes during its life cycle have not been explicitly analyzed. In other models, cytosolic Ca^{2+} changes were studied specifically during mitosis (Hepler, 1992; Takuwa, 1995),

however it is possible that the obtained results were influenced by the technical limitations of the tools available at the time of the experiments (middle 80-ies-to-middle 90-ies). Nevertheless, in these studies it was determined that, with few exceptions, cell division requires an increased cytosolic Ca^{2+} level (Hepler, 1992). This positive regulation is achieved through Ca^{2+} -dependent mRNA transcription of key players in the regulation of eukaryotic cell cycle progression: *cdc2* (=CDK1) and CDK2, cyclin A, cyclin E and a E2F transcription factors (Takuwa et al., 1995; Humeau et al., 2017). Proliferation is as well promoted by the Calcium Release-Activated Channel (CRAC) activity, and the resulting Ca^{2+} oscillations induce NFAT- and NF κ B-mediated activation of genes promoting cell cycle progression or triggering cell death (Humeau et al., 2017).

As inferred above, the very low cytosolic Ca^{2+} level, like the one displayed by aggregating *Dictyostelium* cells, may as well constitute a plausible mechanism of sensitivity increase toward Ca^{2+} transients of lower magnitude induced by low concentrations of chemoattractants — a property that might be required for successful orientation. This possibility apparently has not been analyzed yet, although some evidence exist that can be read in this way: increasing the cytosolic Ca^{2+} level in *Dictyostelium* either by caffeine or A23187+ Ca^{2+} treatments impairs chemotaxis (Brenner and Thoms, 1984; Abe et al., 1988; Jaiswal et al., 2012). A similar mechanism of cellular *adaptation* to stimuli of different strengths (on the background of which the meaningful signal can still be detected) can be proposed. On the other hand, maintaining the background level of cytosolic Ca^{2+} under different conditions probably requires different energy spending from the organism; this aspect may further link background Ca^{2+} level to Ca^{2+} signaling robustness (section 5.). We should note that an alternative strategy of Ca^{2+} sensitivity increase has already been observed in phylogenetically distant organisms, by rising calmodulin expression levels (Kahl and Means, 2003).

A general conclusion from this section is that on long time scales in living cells and organisms it is hard to identify something corresponding to a *background Ca^{2+} level* in its traditional meaning: different stages of cellular development require different levels of Ca^{2+} or calcium transients with specific spatio-temporal characteristics, and thus, this level does not remain the same over time. On the other hand, the mechanisms providing the required amount of Ca^{2+} in “resting” conditions in many cases are those same that underlie the large Ca^{2+} fluxes, differing only in the grade of their activity. In addition, the presence of Ca^{2+} microdomains and endosomal Ca^{2+} -releasing “point” sources indicate —somehow against the generalized *low background Ca^{2+} level* concept— that this ion distribution in the cytosol is (permanently?) quite heterogeneous. In this way, background cytosolic Ca^{2+} dynamics, although hardly appreciable on its own (unlike migration or chemotaxis), nevertheless provides a direct link between the different classes of “observable” cellular-scale Ca^{2+} -dependent phenomena.

2.2 Ca²⁺ signaling in the migration-chemotaxis functional block

A distinctive feature of animal cells is their ability to crawl over substrates by changes in their shape. Although a compendium of cellular locomotion principles was published very recently (Miyata et al., 2020), the origin of this remarkable ability of animal cells has attracted surprisingly little attention. Unlike animal cells, plant cells evolved behind cell walls, and this was probably one of the reasons why vegetal cells lost the ability to actively change their shape. Nevertheless, both animal and some vegetal cells use an extension of their body (either branched, in the case of animal cells, or in the form of a single protuberance, in the case of root hairs or pollen tubes) to expand their limits, accompanied by the whole cell displacement (in the case of animal cells), or to achieve growth (in the case of vegetal ones). In both cases such expansion can be sensitive to external stimuli, which may drive it in a specific direction. In the particular case of chemical stimuli this property is known as chemotaxis (Artemenko et al., 2014; Paupe and Prudent, 2018). Below we describe the structural organization of the machinery that underlie the cellular ability to migrate, and the Ca²⁺ functional block that regulates its functioning.

2.2.1. Cell migration types and transitions between them

Traditionally, two cell migration types over substrates have been distinguished: amoeboid and mesenchymal, which can be observed in different cell types under the same external conditions. Moreover, a same cell type can also switch between migration modes under certain conditions, suggesting that migration modes are extremi in a continuum space rather than independent phenomena (Huttenlocher and Horwitz, 2011; Liu et al., 2015).

Amoeboid migration is considered more primitive, as it only weakly depends on the integrin-mediated substrate adhesion mechanism which is typically involved in mesenchymal migration (Artemenko et al., 2014; Krakhmal et al., 2015; Bodor et al., 2020). Amoeboid migration is fast and it is characterized by quick cell deformation (rapid protrusion and retraction of pseudopods), and adaptation to the shape of the extracellular matrix, without its degradation (Artemenko et al., 2014; Krakhmal et al., 2015; Sao et al., 2019; Yamada and Sixt, 2019; Bodor et al., 2020). In cells using this mode of migration the nucleus shape can be altered (Krakhmal et al., 2015; Bodor et al., 2020). Examples of cells that crawl using this migration mode are *Dictyostelium*, leukocytes and metastatic cells of certain tumors (Artemenko et al., 2014).

Unlike amoeboid migration, mesenchymal one relies on lamellipodia, the dynamics of which depends on actin polymerization (Krakhmal et al., 2015; Bodor et al., 2020). In mesenchymal migration, integrin acts as a bridge connecting the extracellular matrix with the actin network (Yamada and Sixt, 2019). Mesenchyme migration mode, in addition, is associated with degradation of the extracellular matrix by metalloproteases.

Switching between migration modes is cell type-dependent, and some cells can display blebs in addition to lamellipodia (Bodor et al., 2020). Together, three parameters are

currently considered responsible for switching between migration modes: adhesion, confinement, and cell contractility (Liu et al., 2015; Fig 3). Adhesion—together with stress fibers formation—inhibits fast amoeboid migration (Bodor et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2015), while absence of focal adhesions is sufficient to induce a quick switch to amoeboid migration (Liu et al., 2015). Mechanical load (confinement) under low adhesion conditions results in the appearance of several migration phenotypes, depending on the cell line: mesenchymal NHDF cells were shown to increase their contractility, acquiring a round shape with blebs, and becoming mostly immotile (Liu et al., 2015; Bodor et al., 2020)—curiously, a behavior which is reminiscent of pluripotent stem cells in culture (YP—unpublished observations). However, in this and other cell lines (both mesenchymal and amoeboid) under such conditions two different migration types can spontaneously appear, in different proportions: a faster A2 type—with cells displaying an elongated body and a pronounced uropod, and a slightly slower A1 type—with rounded cells displaying a small protrusion at the leading edge (Liu et al., 2015). The switch to either A2 or A1 migration depends on high or low myosin-mediated cell contractility, respectively, and in the case of A1 mode an additional polarizing stimulus is required (Liu et al., 2015). Each migration type is based on a specific mechanism: A2 is based on global retrograde (from the cell's front to the back) cortical actin flow, while A1 movement relies on local actin polymerization at frontral protrusions (Liu et al., 2015). Confinement induces a fast (within 20 s) switch to bleb-mediated migration in the amoeboid-crawling *Dictyostelium*, which is reversed back to pseudopod protrusion within 8-10 mins upon the load withdrawal. As in mesenchymal cells, compression of *Dictyostelium* cells was shown to induce their contractility increase and polarity loss (“rounding”), accompanied by a reduction in the cell adhesion (Srivastava et al., 2020). Interestingly, confinement was also reported to induce a switch from swimming to the amoeboid-like *metaboly* movement in the unicellular eukaryote *Euglena* (Noselli et al., 2019).

Intracellular components that influence cell's mechanical properties can also affect the migration type. Vimentin and lamin are examples of such components. Lamin makes cell nuclei stiffer (Yamada and Sixt, 2019), while the loss of vimentin was shown to make cells less stiff and to increase their motility in 3D (but not in 2D) environments (Patteson et al., 2019). Curiously, this last finding is in contrast with the higher vimentin expression being associated with epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition (EMT) and thus—to a higher metastatic potential (Patteson et al., 2019), and with invasive cells being considered stiffer than control ones (Mierke, 2020). Together, cells' interaction with the extracellular matrix and mechanical properties of the cells themselves define their migration routes: either along extracellular matrix fibers in the case of mesenchymal cells, or through pore lumens in the case of amoeboid cells (Mierke, 2020). In this way, mechanical properties of the extracellular matrix can guide the direction of cell migration.

Cells using either of the major migration types display no apparent differences in their ability to chemotax: in mice, mutant dendritic cells lacking focal adhesions display no difference in their speed, persistence, or their efficiency to localize to lymph nodes, compared to WT ones (Bodor et al., 2020). Nevertheless, differences are appreciable in the chemotaxis-induced polarization of cells exhibiting different migration types: for example, in mesenchymal cells the microtubule organizing center is located to the front of the nucleus, whereas in amoeboid cells this center and cell organelles are located behind the nucleus (Yamada and Sixt, 2019). Cell shape is apparently linked to chemotaxis accuracy: in shallow chemoattractant gradients *Dictyostelium* amoebas display a “tasting behavior” splitting and elongating their pseudopodes, while in steep gradients their movement is nearly straight (Bodor et al., 2020). Similarly, cells appear to be able to estimate energy costs associated with particular pathways, and to choose their migration route according to such estimation (Zanotelli et al., 2019).

2.2.2. Ca^{2+} signaling structure responsible for cell traction and fine tuning of migration direction

2.2.2.1. Cell traction and chemotaxis machinery

In migration types that involve adhesion, forces are directed from the cell periphery toward its center, where myosin normally accumulates (Edwards-Jorquera et al., 2020). These forces drive the so-called centripetal retrograde flow. Meanwhile, in non-adhesive migration types forces are exerted in the opposite direction (Bodor et al., 2020). Together, the forces that propel cells forward are provided by F-actin and myosin (Mierke, 2020).

Polarization and symmetry breaking was shown to depend on the endosome-localized Wnt5a receptor-actomyosin polarity (WRAMP) structure, which regulates polarized F-actin and myosin IIB localization in a Wnt5a-dependent manner, promoting in this way invasion (Mierke, 2020). This effect depends on the transient binding of the WRAMP structure to actin and myosin and the localized Ca^{2+} increase induced by this structure (Mierke, 2020). WRAMP expression levels are high in metastatic melanomas and at the invasive edge of primary tumors, the cells of which can migrate toward lymph nodes, suggesting the participation of the WRAMP structure in chemotaxis (Mierke, 2020).

Lamellipodia at the cell leading edge grow by actin polymerization, a process that depends on Rac1 (which controls actin branching), Cdc42, WASP/WAVE and Arp2/3. These same proteins maintain migration and confer directionality to it (Mierke, 2020). In general, polarization events at the cell front are studied much better than those at the cell rear (Mierke, 2020).

Mesenchymal-amoeboid transition was shown to depend on the contractility increase of rear-polarized myosin II — a process that is promoted by the enhanced activation of RhoA/ROCK, and which induces the global retrograde flow of actin (Krakhamal et al.,

2015; Yamada and Sixt, 2019). RhoA-activated myosin II contractility facilitates the cell's rear retraction during migration, but can also participate in the retraction of actin protrusions at the cell's leading edge (Edwards-Jorquera et al., 2020). Myosin can also be redistributed under different stimuli: load-induced blebbing in *Dictyostelium* is accompanied by a quick myosin II recruitment to the cell cortex (Srivastava et al., 2020). Thus, Rac1-dependent cell spreading is apparently enabled when RhoA activity is reduced by integrin binding to the extracellular matrix (Mierke, 2020).

Overall, the chosen migration mode —mesenchymal or amoeboid— apparently depends on the proportion of Rac1/RhoA signaling — i.e., actin polymerization or contraction, and is not strictly linked to some particular cell shape (Krakhmal et al., 2015; Mierke, 2020).

2.2.2.2. Ca^{2+} as a general mediator in the traction mechanism

The polarization of the machinery responsible for migration and chemotaxis (described in the previous section), activation of the involved GPCRs, and actomyosin contractility are processes that depend on Ca^{2+} .

In cells displaying amoeboid migration, a polarized distribution of cytosolic Ca^{2+} has been reported, with an increased Ca^{2+} concentration at the cell rear (where myosin is located) compared to the frontal edge, where a higher activity of plasma membrane Ca^{2+} ATPases maintains a lower level of this ion (Yumura et al., 1996; Ritaine et al., 2017; Paupe and Prudent, 2018). Such Ca^{2+} distribution looks opposite to the *tip-focused* gradients observed in other actively-protruding structures like growing axonal cones or pollen tubes (Rudd and Franklin-Tong, 2001). However, despite the relatively low Ca^{2+} level at the leading edges of migrating cells, localized Ca^{2+} “flickers” can be detected at these sites (references at the beginning of this section and Tsai et al., 2015), and these flickers are required for chemotaxis-driven cell migration (Okeke et al., 2016; Paupe and Prudent, 2018).

Interestingly, in fibroblasts a generalized and sustained cytosolic Ca^{2+} increase induced by Ca^{2+} ionophore application produces the retraction of the rear edge, mimicking changes taking place during their migration, but this increase additionally expands to the leading edge, preventing the ability of cells to move (Goldfine et al., 1981). Similarly, in *Drosophila* hemocytes, a general cytosolic Ca^{2+} increase induced by thapsigargin application makes them static (Edwards-Jorquera et al., 2020). Migration inhibition by the cytosolic Ca^{2+} increase seemingly has a threshold: similar treatment in *Xenopus* gastrula induces higher migratory activity of the mesoderm leading edge (Paudel et al., 2018), probably by increasing the contractility of these cells, as described above. A transient global Ca^{2+} increase, on the other hand, is observed during cell rear detachment (Déliot and Constantin, 2015).

In animal cells, the traction mechanism apparently depends on Ca^{2+} release mediated by IP_3 Rs: inhibition of these channels by caffeine reportedly impairs migration, while

inhibition of ER-located RYRs does not affect it (Ritaine et al., 2017). In *Dictyostelium*, a line with the non-functional IP₃R-like gene, *iplA*, displays no altered response to the natural chemoattractants cAMP and folic acid, but lacks sensitivity to Ca²⁺ gradients (Traynor et al., 2000). This observation indicates how IP₃Rs are involved in the migration-chemotaxis functional block: their activity is required for motility, but the direction in which the cells move (and apparently — the intracellular sites at which IP₃Rs are activated) is determined by other factors (see section 2.4.1.3.). In cancer cells, the increased activity of IP₃Rs, together with an increased background Ca²⁺ level and the associated higher cell contractility (see section 2.4.3.), can underlie their higher migration ability.

2.2.2.3. Does Ca²⁺ signaling play a fine tuning role during chemotaxis?

Migration is intrinsically linked to directionality (“if there is migration — it has a direction”). Nevertheless, it can be expected that different cells evolved different mechanisms to fine tune their migration direction according to physiologically relevant stimuli. Thus, although traction mechanisms themselves are to some degree conserved, higher variability can be expected in the input signals that activate them.

Ca²⁺ influx from the extracellular medium is not consistently required for motility itself (its long-term effect apparently depends on the extent to which intracellular stores are filled through SOCE), although different cells have different requirements of this Ca²⁺ source for orientation (Yumura et al., 1996; Traynor et al., 2000). An example of transporters that transduce external stimuli into Ca²⁺ influx are channels of the TRP family (Canales et al., 2019). For instance, in cells migrating through narrow pores, TRPM7 was proposed to serve as a barosensor of hydraulic resistance (Bodor et al., 2020), responsible for Ca²⁺ flickers that control direction of cells’ migration, but not speed (Ritaine et al., 2017). This same stretch-activated channel is important for metastasis of prostate, breast and lung cancers (Déliot and Constantin, 2015). In these cases, TRPM7 regulates focal adhesions dynamics through calpain/CAMKII that activate myosin light chain kinase and focal adhesion kinase, which in turn control intracellular myosin dynamics (Déliot and Constantin, 2015). Interestingly, in the absence of Ca²⁺ flickers cell movement is faster, but the chemotaxis ability is impaired (Déliot and Constantin, 2015).

In *Dictyostelium*, the Piezo channel mediates the cell’s sensitivity to compression, directing the morphological change from pseudopods to blebs, induced by increased cellular contractility — processes that in this organism depend on extracellular Ca²⁺ (Srivastava et al., 2020). Interestingly, in Piezo-null cells chemotaxis is affected, although mutant cells move at the same speed as normal ones. In this cells, myosin II is still recruited to the cortex upon stimulation with cAMP, but this occurs even in the absence of extracellular Ca²⁺, and in the IP₃R-null (*IplA*) mutant it takes place without a visible cytosolic Ca²⁺ increase (Srivastava et al., 2020). These results suggest the possibility that other localized Ca²⁺ sources are required for chemotaxis.

2.2.2.4. *Signaling from acidic Ca²⁺ stores can couple traction and chemotaxis regulation*
Among intracellular organelles, probably only acidic Ca²⁺ stores (Patel and Muallem, 2011; Patel and Cai., 2015) can behave as individual and largely independent Ca²⁺-releasing compartments. This property results from their organization, which differs in different taxonomic groups: in metazoans they resemble swarms of little organelles, while in plants and fungi their analog, the vacuole, tends to appear as a unified compartment, rarely split. The possibility that the plant vacuole can participate in localized Ca²⁺ signaling has been suggested in the literature (Pérez et al., 2008), however, a larger set of smaller and independent compartments is more suitable to produce controlled and spatially-confined Ca²⁺ signals within cells. From this viewpoint, the lack of crawling movements in vegetal cells (Alberts et al., 2008) resulted-from-and-allowed-them to develop and maintain during evolution a large single vacuole, the functions of which evolved in directions different from those of the endolysosomal system in animal cells.

Thus, can the number and size of acidic Ca²⁺ stores (influencing the Ca²⁺ transients they can generate) be a determinant in conferring the ability to change the shape/crawl in animal cells? This looks like an *ad hoc* explanation, as the importance of the endolysosomal system for cell migration has indeed been established (Raffaello et al., 2016; Sáez et al., 2018; Edwards-Jorquera et al., 2020). However, to the best of our knowledge, the influence of the physical properties of acidic Ca²⁺ stores on the cells' ability to crawl has not been analyzed yet.

Interestingly, Ca²⁺ exchange between lysosomes and the ER (the main apparent source of Ca²⁺ for traction in animal cells) has been reported: Ca²⁺ released from lysosomes can trigger IP₃R-mediated Ca²⁺ release (“chattering”, Patel and Brailou, 2011). On the other hand, results have been obtained showing that is the ER, and not the pH gradient the force driving calcium refilling of lysosomes (Garrity et al., 2016).

In fungi (yeasts) Ca²⁺ release from the vacuole is a well-established phenomenon (Denis and Cyert, 2002), whereas for plants, despite existing evidence of the central vacuole participation in Ca²⁺ signaling, direct proofs of vacuolar Ca²⁺ release are still missing (Schönknecht, 2013).

In mammalian (and other animal) cells a particular feature of the endosomal system is its ability to release Ca²⁺ in response to nicotinic acid dinucleotide phosphate (NAADP) application. NAADP is, alongside with another important intracellular Ca²⁺-releasing messenger—cyclic ADP-ribose (cADPR), which targets ER ryanodine receptors—produced by ADP-ribosyl cyclases, a family of enzymes that share a close similarity even in organisms as phylogenetically distant as humans and mollusks (i.e., *Aplysia californica*; States et al., 1992). Moreover, an ADP-ribosyl cyclase has been described in *Euglena gracilis* (Masuda et al., 1999), a unicellular organism that despite possessing plant-related features (chloroplasts and autotrophy), lacks a rigid cell wall and is able to perform

ameboid-like movements (“metaboly”). The ability of the *Euglena* ADPR-cyclase to synthesize NAADP, however, has seemingly not been analyzed yet, and apparently this enzyme is not an homolog of the *Aplysia* or mammalian ADPR-cyclases (own search using BLASTP, <https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>).

Humans have two ADP-ribosyl cyclase homologs, CD38 (the predominant form) and CD157, both capable of producing NAADP and cADPR, although to different extent. CD38 has been linked to several important diseases, such as impaired social memory in mice (autism in humans), diabetes, HIV infection, and chronic lymphocytic leukemia (Malavasi et al., 2008). Inactivation of this enzyme in humans is seemingly lethal (Lee, 2011). Other important aspects of this enzyme have been extensively reviewed (CD38 evolution — Malavasi et al., 2008; Liu et al., 2009; Quarona et al., 2013; structure and function — Lee, 2006; Zhao et al., 2012). Plants lack ADP-ribosyl cyclases, although *Aplysia* ADP-ribosyl cyclase heterologously expressed in the *Arabidopsis* plant is activated by abscisic acid (ABA, the “drought phytohormone”), resulting in an increase in the intracellular cADPR level. This cADPR increase, in turn, induces the expression of a set of ABA-activated genes, from which it was concluded that cADPR mediates ABA-induced signaling in plants (Sánchez et al., 2004). NAADP was reported to induce Ca^{2+} release from ER-derived endosomes in plants (Navazio et al., 2000), although no subsequent work was published further exploring this phenomenon.

Currently, there are no known regulators of CD38 enzymatic activity. Instead, in mammalian cells it has been recently shown that NAADP production is upregulated by CD38 translocation to lysosomes (Fang et al., 2018), in agreement with observations made previously on the importance of pH for the resulting product (either cADPR, synthesized at neutral pH, or NAADP, synthesized at low pH; Lee et al., 2002). Importantly, while NAADP synthesis requires an acidic intralysosomal environment, Ca^{2+} refilling of lysosome-like organelles apparently involves both *pH-dependent* (Cation Exchangers, CAXs, in vacuoles of plants and fungi, or lysosomes in non-placental mammals; coupled activity of the $\text{Na}^+/\text{H}^+ - \text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchangers in lysosomes of animals), and *pH-independent* mechanisms (through the activity of IP_3Rs in the ER of animals cells) (Faris et al., 2019). It is thus probable that endosomes are able to constantly maintain a certain level of Ca^{2+} , but release it differently —through different Ca^{2+} -permeable channels— depending on particular gating factors (Faris et al., 2019; Gerndt et al., 2020) that may be present at different points of the organelle trajectory within the cell.

Inactivation of CD38, as mentioned above, indeed affects the cells’ ability to migrate, although it has been shown in very particular contexts (Frasca et al., 2006; Sun et al., 2003; Lin et al., 2017; Chini et al., 2018). However, the existence of a general correlation between the activity of CD38 homologs and the cell’ ability to migrate or the rate of migration has not yet been explicitly proven.

TPC-mediated Ca²⁺ signaling is involved in chemotaxis

In animal cells, lysosome-localized two pore calcium channels (TPCs) and ER-located ryanodine receptors (RYRs) have been proposed as targets of NAADP (the latter—apparently through an additional subunit) (Guse and Diercks, 2018).

TPCs in animal cells are activated and able to release Ca²⁺ under stimulation with phosphatidylinositol 3,5-bisphosphate, PI(3,5)P₂, and NAADP (reviewed in Grimm et al., 2017). In the case of the animal TPC2 channels, application of either of these agonist induces a selectivity switch: NAADP increases Ca²⁺ selectivity of the channels, whereas PI(3,5)P₂ increases the Na⁺ selectivity of the channel (Gerndt et al., 2020).

Plant TPC homologs are activated by neither of these two messengers (Boccaccio et al., 2014), requiring instead a cytosolic Ca²⁺ increase, sensed through EF-hand motifs present in the cytosolic domain (Hedrich et al., 2018). Other relevant properties of these channels are discussed in several recent reviews (Hedrich and Marten, 2011; Hedrich et al., 2018 — for plant homologs; Kintzer and Stroud, 2017 — for animal ones). TPCs are absent in fungi and many algae (Schönknecht, 2013; Cai et al., 2015 and references therein). Important for the subject of this section, functional TPC channels are essential for animal cells' migration, as was first reported in relation to invasiveness of cancer cells (Nguyen et al., 2017). TPCs control the ability of cells to migrate by regulating the intracellular vesicle trafficking and the concomitant trafficking of adhesion proteins, particularly — integrins (Nguyen et al., 2017). In addition, Ca²⁺ signals evoked by NAADP activate the focal adhesion kinase (FAK), which is required for cell migration (Faris et al., 2019). Interestingly, intracellular vesicles carrying TPC2 channels start moving slower upon application of NAADP, while in similar conditions a PI(3,5)P₂-like agonist induces lysosomal exocytosis (Gerndt et al., 2020).

TPCs' activity induced by PI(3,5)P₂ and NAADP is inhibited under nutrient-rich conditions by the mammalian target of rapamycin, mTOR, and by ATP (Cang et al., 2013; Faris et al., 2019), although it seemingly has not been tested whether starvation provokes activation of these channels. Despite the gaps in the understanding of TPCs physiology, the results described above suggest that—at least in mammalian cells—these channels can function as starvation-triggered chemotactic drivers, activating the IP₃Rs-dependent cell propulsive machinery. TPCs appear to be a highly versatile convergent point transducing the cell metabolic status into localized Ca²⁺ signals directing cell movement.

Importantly, some organisms do not carry TPC channels, nor ADP-ribosyl cyclase homologs in their endolysosomal compartments. Examples are the Ecdysozoans *Caenorhabditis elegans* and *Drosophila melanogaster* (Ferrero and Malavasi, 2002; Patel et al., 2010). *C. elegans* migratory cells do not display noticeable ameboid movements (Schwarz et al., 2012), whereas *Drosophila* possesses typical migratory immune cells

(Stramer et al., 2005; Fauvarque and Williams, 2011). Dissociated cells of both organisms are able to crawl in culture, suggesting that TPCs are dispensable in these cells. Curiously, *Drosophila* primary hemocytes do not migrate when plated on 2D surfaces (Edwards et al., 2018) — a phenotype somehow resembling that of cells lacking vimentin (Patteson et al., 2019). Clarification of how TPCs absence is compensated in these cells should shed light on the role TPCs play in chemotaxis and chemotaxis-driven migration in other metazoans.

TRPMLs-mediated Ca²⁺ signaling regulates cell traction

Another lysosomal Ca²⁺-permeable channel, also activated by PI(3,5)P₂ (see Supplementary Note), is the transient receptor potential mucolipin channel 1 (TRPML1). TRPML1-mediated Ca²⁺ release is important for the centripetal retrograde movement of myosin II and for activation of this protein at the cell rear, promoting cell contraction and forward movement (Bretou et al., 2017; Edwards-Jorquera et al., 2020). This role of TRPML is similar to that of the WRAMP structure, which also participates in symmetry breaking (see section 2.2.2.1.), suggesting a possible functional coupling between TRPMLs and WRAMPs. Hemocytes from TRPML-null fruit flies migrate more slowly than control ones, and their migration occurs without actin protrusions but with bleb-like structures at the trailing edge. Nevertheless, mutant cells display no altered directionality, suggesting that TRPMLs are not involved in chemotaxis (Edwards-Jorquera et al., 2020). Moreover, TRPML1 activity is required for centripetal movement of lysosomes themselves, forming part of an “on-demand mechanism regulating lysosome motility, positioning and tubulation” (Li et al., 2016). In mammalian cells, TRPML1 regulates the lysosomes’ size by promoting their fission (Zou et al., 2015; Cao et al., 2017; Di Paola et al., 2018; Edwards-Jorquera et al., 2020), which likely contributes to the maintenance of the spatio-temporal heterogeneity of the intracellular Ca²⁺-release sources. Even more, TRPML1 stimulates lysosomal biogenesis and autophagy through calcineurin-dependent activation of TFEB, the master transcriptional regulator of this process (Sardiello et al., 2009; Settembre et al., 2011).

Plants (streptophytes) lack TRP homologs (Chang et al., 2010), although *Chlamydomonas*, which does not crawl (but possesses a contractile vacuole), has an extended TRP channels family (Bickerton et al., 2016; Plattner, 2018). Yeasts, which display vacuolar fragmentation under hyperosmotic stress (Li et al., 2010), express a vacuole-residing homolog of animal TRPs (Yvc1p) which releases Ca²⁺ from the vacuole under this condition (Denis and Cyert, 2002; Zhou et al., 2003).

Does intracellular lysosomal dynamics support the role of acidic Ca²⁺ stores in migration/chemotaxis?

A hint to the role that lysosomal Ca²⁺ signals can play in cellular migration can be obtained by the analysis of intracellular lysosomal dynamics. First, these compartments participate in

the turnover of Rac1, which is required for the formation of actin protrusions (Edwards-Jorquera et al., 2020). In several cell types, including TPC-lacking primary *Drosophila* hemocytes, upon chemotaxis-induced cell polarization lysosomes redistribute to the cell rear, where myosin II is localized (Edwards et al., 2018). Lysosomal centripetal redistribution in hemocytes depends on TRPML1 and is coupled to phagocytosis, as inhibition of the latter reduces the hemocyte migration speed (Edwards-Jorquera et al., 2020). On the other hand, direct lysosome transport into the axon (to the leading edge) is required for axonal cone growth in neurons (Farías et al., 2017).

Assuming the importance of the endolysosomal compartments size for migration ability, it can be expected that treatments artificially increasing endolysosomes size (=inducing vacuolization) would also affect cellular migration. Indeed, this has been observed: vacuolin, a compound that promotes mammalian cells vacuolization through the activation of Rab5 and lysosomal alcalinization, and prevents endosome-lysosomal fusion (Lu, 2014), affects the ability of cells to migrate (Liu et al., 2012; Lu, 2014). A similar effect has been observed in cells that accumulate phagocytosed material (Mierke, 2020) or are subjected to other treatments reported to produce vacuolization (Catrenich and Chestnut, 1992; Henics and Wheathley, 1999; Qin et al., 2006; Bandyopadhyay et al., 2014; Shubin et al., 2016). However, to determine the contribution of the organelle size to migration in these cases, it has to be established whether luminal pH and Ca^{2+} levels remain intact. Of note, acquisition of a malignant phenotype leads to lysosomes' volume increase (Faris et al., 2019), suggesting that in these cells the lysosomal size increase follows other intracellular changes (for example, a contractility increase).

From the information presented above, we can tentatively propose the following general functions for lysosomal channels:

- 1) In animal cells, TRPML channels appear to be essential regulators of the *number* (Sardiello et al., 2009; Settembre et al., 2011) and *size* (Cao et al., 2017) of lysosomes — a property that apparently was critical for animal cells to acquire the ability to perform ameboid movements. Plants cells, on their hand, apparently lost this ability during evolution, owing to their sedentary lifestyle. Nevertheless, TRP homologs have been conserved in organisms possessing a contractile vacuole. Control of lysosomes' size in animal cells is probably required to produce highly localized Ca^{2+} signals at different parts of the cell.
- 2) TPCs apparently mediate chemotaxis-triggered migration: the “external” migration, i.e., cell crawling by shape change in animal cells, and, possibly, the “internal” migration by reshaping the vacuolar membrane in plant cells (see Supplementary Note). TPCs underlie the ability of animal cells to migrate by controlling the traffic of endosomes and, concomitantly, the traffic of proteins required for cell adhesion and self-pulling, modulating these processes according to the cell metabolic state. The plant endosomal system seems to

function primarily as a (receptors) trafficking system (Bar and Avni, 2014), in which the vacuole probably plays the role of a unifying compartment that “brings distant parts of the cell to a common ground” by promoting communication between them (see Gu et al., 2017).

Essentially the same roles have been suggested for TPC and TRPML1 channels in dendritic cells (Sáez et al., 2018), further supporting the possibility that these proteins are involved in a conserved mechanism underlying animal cells’ ability to crawl and chemotax, rather than represent some distinctive feature of a particular cell type. The conserved character of this pathway complicates reducing the ability of cancers to metastasize by targeting endolysosomal channels and/or CD38 (see Grimm et al., 2018).

Although lysosomal Ca^{2+} permeable channels have been shown to mediate migration, a general role of lysosomes in this process remains unclear: they seem to be both the source of agonists inducing Ca^{2+} release, and the target of these agonists. How each role is chosen in each case, and how these roles may interact is currently unknown, although evidence suggests that luminal pH changes might be involved. Nevertheless, results obtained to date suggest that lysosomes could mediate localized volumetric Ca^{2+} transients.

Interestingly, mature vegetal cells display a large single vacuole, but during development at meristems, their vacuolar system is initially fragmented (Marty, 1999). Whether such architecture is important for Ca^{2+} signaling in these cells, and whether Ca^{2+} signaling from prevacuoles exists at all is currently unknown.

2.2.2.5. Mitochondrial Ca^{2+} signaling in cellular migration

Mitochondria are other intracellular organelles that play an important role in cellular migration (Rafaello et al., 2016; White, 2017) by providing energy supply at the cell leading edge (Zanotelli et al., 2019). In addition, mitochondrial calcium uniporters (MCU) and mitochondrial calcium uptake proteins 1 (MICU1) are important for migration (Rafaello et al., 2016; Paupe and Prudent, 2018). Curiously, defects in these proteins result in opposite changes in mitochondrial Ca^{2+} load, but in both cases cellular migration is inhibited (Paupe and Prudent, 2018). It has been proposed that this inhibition results from impaired Ca^{2+} translocation from the ER to mitochondria, but the mechanism has not been elucidated.

Cell migration requires mitochondrial ROS (mtROS), which release into the cytoplasm is proposed to occur through the Ca^{2+} -permeable VDAC1 channel, essential for cell migration (Shoshan-Barmatz et al., 2017a; Shoshan-Barmatz et al., 2017b). Importantly, mtROS release requires the presence of functional MCU and MICU1 (Paupe and Prudent, 2018). ROS are known activators of TPCs in plants (Islam et al., 2010), although we could not find reports of a similar analysis conducted for the animal counterparts. In humans, VDAC1-3 interact with TPCs (Lin-Moshier et al., 2014), and if animal TPC homologs are

also activated by mtROS, it could provide an additional explanation of mitochondria relocation to the leading edge of migrating cells, in addition to buffering of the extracellular Ca^{2+} influx (Paupe and Prudent, 2018). We further analyze the relationship between mitochondria and cell migration in section 2.3.4.

In addition, mitochondria fission promotes the highly migratory phenotype of cancer cells (Denisenko et al., 2019), and this effect is very similar to the proposed influence of the size of acidic Ca^{2+} stores on migratory properties of normal cells.

2.3 The role of Ca^{2+} signaling in the proliferation-quiescence-based functional block

The absence of both migration and chemotaxis in plants suggests that the Ca^{2+} -dependent mechanisms regulating these phenomena could have evolved as a functional block characteristic of the animal lineage. In contrast, the macroscopic Ca^{2+} -dependent processes that will be examined in this section (proliferation, quiescence, differentiation and apoptosis) are present in all multicellular lineages and thus, can be supposed to constitute a functional block separate from the migration-chemotaxis one. However, in cancer (a spectrum of diseases of the animal lineage), regulation of both apoptosis and differentiation is affected, suggesting that Ca^{2+} signaling involved in these particular programs might be independent from the Ca^{2+} signaling that maintains the proliferation-quiescence core. A specific association of apoptosis and differentiation with multicellularity (unlike proliferation and quiescence) supports this hypothesis (see Meikrantz and Schlegel, 1995). It is important to recall, however, that the possibility to delimit these programs does not imply that they can be mechanically isolated, as a strong link between them remains in the form of shared Ca^{2+} transporters, Ca^{2+} stores/sources, and Ca^{2+} -independent mechanisms involving common Ca^{2+} -storing organelles. In addition, these programs can interact. Thus, interventions targetting a particular transporter should take into account the different functional blocks it is involved in, as well as the changes to which functional blocks or programs are subjected during either normal or aberrant development.

In the case of the migration-chemotaxis block, the properties of lysosome-derived Ca^{2+} signaling seem to be a key factor underlying cells' ability to migrate. Contrary to this, in cancer the low relevance of particular Ca^{2+} sources for cell homeostasis has been stated numerous times. Thus, to understand how Ca^{2+} signaling is established and self-regulated during the developmental process (either normal, or aberrant, in the form of cancer), it is necessary to know how indispensable is the Ca^{2+} influx mediated by a specific transporter for the execution of a particular program. An insight into this issue can be gained from the difference in the families of Ca^{2+} transporters present in different lineages. For example, during their evolution, plants lost voltage-gated calcium channels (VGCCs, still found in the charophyte alga *Klebsormidium flaccidum*), IP_3Rs , ATP-gated purinergic channels (P2XR_s), cys-loop superfamily of ligand-gated ion channels (Cys-loops), TRPs (Edel et al., 2017) and RYRs, most of which were apparently present in the last universal common ancestor of chlorophytes and streptophytes. The phylogenetic distribution of these channels

suggests that their loss took place before land colonization by plants (Edel et al., 2017). Meanwhile, these channels are indispensable for differentiation of animal cells, suggesting a drastic difference in the ways by which differentiation is achieved in the animal and plant lineages. This difference probably also underlies the higher differentiation depth distinctive of animal cells, and different ways by which plant and animal morphologies are established (see Pérez Koldenkova and Hatsugai, 2018 for a related discussion). Thus, although the functional block in question is based on the proliferation-quiescence tandem, different lineages developed different mechanisms of exit toward differentiation and apoptosis — programs that are required within a multicellular organism, and which are functionally realized in the particular background of preserved elements of the Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit. For the moment, we will consider differentiation and apoptosis as programs belonging to the proliferation-quiescence functional block, and in section 2.4.2. we will validate this assumption. Importantly, the mutual exclusivity of the proliferation-quiescence and migration-chemotaxis functional blocks does not mean that acidic stores are exempted from functions in the former.

We postulate a tight interconnection between different programs and functional blocks they compose, but it seems reasonable to start the analysis of the proliferation-quiescence-based functional block by examining how Ca^{2+} signaling is organized in stem cells.

2.3.1. Stemness

Stem cells are characteristic of both the animal and plant lineages. At least in animal cells, depending on their origin, “degrees of stemness” can be identified (probably, as a feature opposite to the “differentiation depth” mentioned above), and in this hierarchy embryonic stem cells are the less differentiated ones (and non-migrating, in contrast to the more differentiated multipotent stem cells (*YP* — unpublished observations)).

To the best of our knowledge, electrophysiological characterization of plant stem cells, isolated either from meristems or calli, has not been attempted yet. Low-intensity electrical stimulation has been shown to increase several folds the regeneration of plantlets from calli (Rathore and Goldsworthy, 1985; Rathore et al., 1988), indicating the activation of differentiation programs in this condition. The underlying mechanism apparently involves polarized auxin transport (Goldsworthy, 2006).

The Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit in animal stem cells have been characterized in much more detail. Undifferentiated stem cells are non-excitabile, despite the presence of mRNA and protein of T- and L-type VGCCs (Forostyak et al., 2016; Huang et al., 2017). Different types of animal stem cells tested do not respond to glutamate, GABA, oxytocin or depolarization, but most of them can generate a Ca^{2+} transient if stimulated with ATP, indicating the expression of purinergic receptors (Forostyak et al., 2016). Spontaneous oscillations are also occasionally observed, mostly in cells at the G_1/S stage (Kapur et al., 2007), and these oscillations largely depend upon IP_3Rs activation (Kapur et al., 2007;

Huang et al., 2017). In immature neurons, the ATP-induced Ca^{2+} transients are essential for migration during development, and for the preceding proliferation that gives start to migration (Horigane et al., 2019).

Changes in the stem cells' Ca^{2+} signaling taking place during transition to differentiation (we use an established word form, but rather implying “exit from stemness”) are best studied in neural progenitors. In these cells, “stemness exit” is linked to a temporally increased number of Ca^{2+} transients (Forostyak et al., 2016). Interestingly, mediation of such transients by VGCCs gives rise to gene transcription and cell differentiation (Forostyak et al., 2016). In developing chicken auditory neurons, the onset of spontaneous Ca^{2+} transients is accompanied by a change in the distribution of the Ca^{2+} -signaling protein calretinin. Initially it displays a diffused cytosolic distribution, but upon the onset of spontaneous transients it becomes concentrated beneath the plasma membrane (Hack et al., 2000). These findings potentially explain how sensitivity to VGCCs-mediated Ca^{2+} transients is achieved.

Ca^{2+} influx has also been proposed to participate in stem cell state *maintenance* (Ermakov et al., 2018). For instance, *proliferation* and stem cell lineage maintenance in mice was proposed to result from the extrinsic activation of the mGlu5 receptor, which increases Oct3/4 levels and produces a concomitant increase in the cytosolic Ca^{2+} level in the absence of extracellular glutamate. This observation suggests a mechanism by which specification depending on particular background Ca^{2+} levels can be attained during further development (see sections 2.3.5. and 2.4.2.). Meanwhile, endogenous activation of mGlu5 receptors is suggested to keep cells in the undifferentiated state, without affecting their proliferation (Ermakov et al., 2018). Other Ca^{2+} transporters proposed to participate in stemness maintenance are the T-type VGCCs and the LPA receptors, acting mGlu5Rs and LPARs through G α q-mediated PLC β activation (Ermakov et al., 2018). The Ca^{2+} /CaM-CAMKII is another pathway proposed to be involved in pluripotency maintenance (Ermakov et al., 2018). Importantly, these Ca^{2+} -handling proteins also participate in differentiation triggering, but the balance between the possible outcomes (pluripotency/differentiation) is under the control of p53, which is a negative regulator of pluripotency (Ermakov et al., 2018). We should note, however, that in other studies activation of the above transporters was associated with the onset of differentiation (see sections 2.3.5., 2.4.2.). In addition, analysis of Oct3/4 expression is not a sufficient criterion to determine the so-called naïve or cell ground state pluripotency: markers like KLF2, KLF4, TFCP2L (and ESRRB in mice, or KLF17 in humans) need to be analyzed also (Takashima et al., 2014). Thus, participation of Ca^{2+} signaling in pluripotency maintenance requires more careful analysis. Meanwhile, we propose that activation of Ca^{2+} signaling and cytosolic Ca^{2+} level increase *are direct markers of stemness exit*. Interestingly, lysosomes are likely involved in the induction of stemness characteristics in a pH-dependent manner. As Ca^{2+} signaling in acidic

compartments is tightly linked to the luminal pH dynamics, it could point to a mechanism of *stemness induction by reduced Ca^{2+} release from these compartments*.

Taken together, the available evidence suggest that the Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit in stem cells is primarily established following a genetically determined program. This is in agreement with what is postulated by most theories of biological development (Svetlov, 1978).

2.3.2. Proliferation

In multicellular organisms, a “true” cell *cycle* can probably be ascribed to stem cells, which, through asymmetric division, are able to produce daughter cells with two different identities — a first one preserving stemness, whereas the other one is committed to differentiation. Proliferation of the latter should better be characterized as “cell cycling toward terminal differentiation” — more in accordance to the whole organism *development* as a directed and finite process. Thus, proliferation parameters important for morphogenesis in multicellular organisms are cell division rate or doubling time, and the number of times a cell can divide before engaging in either of the programs comprising the proliferation-quiescence functional block. The still controversial question of neurogenesis in the adult hippocamp in mammals is closely related to this issue (Sorrels et al., 2018; Moreno-Jiménez et al., 2019). In plants, the exact number of times a cell can divide before exiting proliferation has apparently not been determined yet, although it is known that external cues can induce precocious differentiation (for example, in root meristems under hyperosmotic stress or drought, Ji et al., 2014 and *VPK*, unpublished data). Whether the number of cell divisions is affected in this case has apparently not been investigated yet.

Several observations suggest that cytosolic Ca^{2+} increase induces proliferation and promotes its rate increase in animals: 1) loss of the plasma membrane Calcium Sensing Receptor (CaSR) in cells normally expressing it, confers stem-like properties to them (Humeau et al., 2017), 2) as mentioned in section 2.1., proliferating cells in culture have a higher background Ca^{2+} level than cells of the same type but acutely isolated (but, how general this rule is, remains to be established), 3) artificial Ca^{2+} increase in oocytes, mimicking fertilization, induces their initial proliferation even in the absence of fertilization itself (Gruppen et al., 2002).

The proliferation-promoting Ca^{2+} influx is mediated by VGCCs, purinergic receptors, or IP_3 Rs. Exit from quiescence (=non-proliferative state) can also be induced by Ca^{2+} influx through plasma membrane TRP channels, or from mitochondria (Kim and Usachev, 2009; Humeau et al., 2017). Of note, all these Ca^{2+} influx routes (TRP, ORAI, VGCCs, also SERCA) can be associated with oncogenesis, consistent with the several-fold higher cytosolic Ca^{2+} levels observed in cancer cells, compared to normal ones (Humeau et al., 2017). Interestingly, in agreement with the proposed mutually-exclusive character of the migration-chemotaxis and proliferation-quiescence-based functional blocks, TPC silencing in mammalian cells does not affect proliferation cell rate (Faris et al., 2019) and, so far,

TPC1 channels have been shown to participate only in the last step of cell division — abscission (Horton et al., 2015), which is associated with movement resumption in daughter cells after mitosis.

Regulation of the cell cycle by Ca^{2+} in animals and fungi is reviewed in detail by Kahl and Means (2003), Déliot and Constantin (2015), and Humeau and collaborators (2017). Some important aspects of this regulation include: 1) the requirement of STIM-mediated SOCE for CDK2-dependent G_1/S transition; in addition G_2/M transition requires SOCE inhibition, mediated by ORAI2 upregulation; 2) the apparent requirement of intracellular stores for the CaM-dependent cyclin E/CDK2 activity, that drives cell progression through the G_1 phase; 3) expression of key components of the animal cell cycle regulatory machinery (CDK1, CDK2, cyclin A, cyclin E and a member of the E2F transcription factors family) is Ca^{2+} -dependent, as it was mentioned in section 2.1. Regulation of the cell cycle by the $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{CaM}/\text{CAMKII}$ and $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{CaN}/\text{NFAT}$ pathways is described by Déliot and Constantin (2015). Of note, these pathways are also intimately involved in animal cell differentiation and tissue specification, establishing a link between these two programs.

Proliferation rates depend, at least partially, on calmodulin (CaM) expression levels. Calmodulin overexpression shortens the cell cycle, particularly the G_1 phase in mammalian cells, in a concentration-dependent manner (Kahl and Means, 2003). In whole organisms, the expression levels of calmodulin (and the associated proliferation rate?) can be a determinant of the organ morphology, as it was shown for the beaks of Darwin finches (Abzhanov et al., 2006; Clapham, 2007) and hyperplasia (overproliferation) in cardiac ventricles of transgenic mice overexpressing CaM in the heart (Kahl and Means, 2003). In plants, the highest CaM levels are also found in the zones of active proliferation — the meristems and cambium (Zielinski, 1998).

In mammalian cells, $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{CaM}$ is required for mitosis and progression through G_1 (the latter is achieved through Rb phosphorylation by the CDK4/cyclin D complex, which is activated by $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{CaM}$; Kahl and Means, 2003; Narasimha et al., 2014). The $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{CaM}/\text{CaN}/\text{NFAT}$ pathway also upregulates transcription of CDK4 and negatively regulates cyclins A2, E, B genes in lymphocytes (Viola et al., 2005; Mognol et al., 2016; Humeau et al., 2017). Meanwhile, calmodulin high-affinity Ca^{2+} -binding function is dispensable for G_1 progression in unicellular eukaryotes such as yeast and other fungi, although their regulatory machinery is similar to the mammalian one (Kahl and Means, 2003).

The machinery of cell cycle regulation in plants also relies on complexes of cyclins and cyclin-dependent kinases (Gutierrez, 2016; Velappan et al., 2017). The levels of these two protein families are regulated by auxins and abscisic acid, which in addition can modulate the activity of CDK complexes (Dudits et al., 2011). D-type cyclins (driving progression through G_1) are targets of cytokinins, and regulation of expression of cyclins D genes

determines the cell number and organ size, as well as root patterning (Dudits et al., 2011). In plants, leaf size and morphology are determined by cell proliferation which in turn is regulated by the auxin-binding protein 1 (ABP1), a protein that controls the transcription of cyclins D and RETINOBLASTOMA-RELATED (RBR, the plant Rb homolog) (Dudits et al., 2011). Ca^{2+} regulates the progression of the plant cell cycle by controlling *p*-RBR dephosphorylation, carried out by protein phosphatase 2A (PP2A), and calcium-dependent, calmodulin-independent and calmodulin-like domain protein kinases (CPKs) which phosphorylate CDK inhibitor proteins of the KRP family (Dudits et al., 2011). The latter are key regulators of the G_1 checkpoint in plants, and are rate-limiting factors of the primary root growth. They also participate in the inhibition of lateral root initiation in *Arabidopsis*, in the establishment of the dorsal-ventral planes of rice leaves, and in the reduction of nematode-induced galls size in *Arabidopsis* by affecting cell cycle progression (Kumar and Larkin, 2017).

Taking together the observations of cell cycle regulation by Ca^{2+} signaling in plants and animals, discussed above, we can conclude that expression and activity of some key components of the regulatory machinery of the metazoan cell cycle are under direct control of Ca^{2+} signaling. In contrast, the cell cycle progression in plants is driven mainly by hormonal and sucrose availability, whereas Ca^{2+} plays a modulating role through activation of cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitors or the PP2A phosphatase (Fig 4). In tissues, such organization of the regulation mechanism allows triggering proliferation at specific time points by onsets of Ca^{2+} increase, and is consistent with the role of Ca^{2+} waves as propagating modulators of context-dependent developmental programs, proposed by us previously (Pérez Koldenkova and Hatsugai, 2018). Ca^{2+} waves have recently been directly visualized in plants, although in this case they were provoked by damaging factors (Toyota et al., 2018).

The cell cycle regulatory pathways, described above may be altered under biotic or abiotic stresses by additional regulators (Kitsios and Doonan, 2011). Of relevance, Ca^{2+} sources involved in proliferation in metazoans are the same that participate in differentiation, suggesting the possibility that proliferation may result in some degree of differentiation (see below).

2.3.3. Quiescence

Quiescence is the fuzziest program of all those presented here. Cell cycle arrest in animal cell cultures can be induced by many not necessarily related conditions: mitogen deprivation, contact inhibition, loss of adhesion, extracellular pH lowering, or overexpression of cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitors, like p21 and p16 (Moore and Lyle, 2011; Aulestia et al., 2018). In plants, known factors able to induce this program are ROS, ABA, auxin (in meristems), and specific activators and cytokinin action (in terminally-differentiated tissues), or changes in the chromatin accessibility (in the case of dormant tissues) (Velappan et al., 2017). Animal stem cells (either normal or cancer) are able to

preserve quiescence even in contact with their progeny and in the presence of mitogens (Moore and Lyle, 2011), although the pathways regulating quiescence in these two cells types apparently rely on different transcription factors of the SLUG and SNAIL family (Stewart et al., 2014; Ye et al., 2015). Whether quiescence is induced as a passive response, or corresponds to an actively maintained state could probably serve as a criterion to discern between the outcomes of the cell cycle arrest provoked by all the disparate conditions mentioned above.

Quiescent cells in animals are characterized by low levels of check point regulators of the cell cycle, cyclin A2 and cyclin E2 (Cheung and Rando, 2013), the expression of which is under the control of the Ca^{2+} /CaM-CaN-NFAT signaling pathway (Viola et al., 2005). In the stem cell niche of the hair follicle, this pathway maintains quiescence by downregulating CDK4 expression (Horsley et al., 2008). In stem cells, quiescence is under control of tumor suppressors p53 and Rb. For instance, muscle progenitors lacking Rb cannot differentiate due to their inability to exit proliferation; similarly, conditional ablation of all Rb family proteins leads to the exhaustion of the quiescent pool of hematopoietic stem cells (Cheung and Rando, 2013), apparently due to their inability to maintain the quiescent state (Moore and Lyle, 2011). Another protein of the Rb family, p130, maintains quiescence of muscular stem cells by blocking their proliferation and suppressing differentiation (Rumman et al., 2015). Other factors that regulate quiescence are CDK inhibitors (p21 and p27), p57 and the Notch pathway (Cheung and Rando, 2013). In the particular case of quiescent cells of the prostate, androgens withdrawal induces apoptosis and involution of this organ (Meikrantz and Schlegel, 1995).

A decrease in the cytosolic Ca^{2+} level arrests cell cycle, but does not induce quiescence (G_0); the later requires SOCE inhibition and an increased capacity of mitochondria to capture cytosolic Ca^{2+} (linked to a change in the mitochondria shape). These transformations have been observed in cancer cells (Stewart et al., 2014, Aulestia et al., 2018), and apparently can take place in normal cells as well (Hong et al., 2019). Although a decrease of the SOCE-mediated Ca^{2+} influx induces quiescence, depletion of STIM1 or ORAI1, responsible for SOCE, activates caspase-3, which is a marker of apoptosis (Humeau et al., 2017). This result may indicate how can Ca^{2+} dynamics be specifically linked to a particular transporter mediating it.

In plants, mitochondria are also involved in quiescence, albeit through ROS and redox signaling (Velappan et al., 2017). Growth arrest was observed in A2 alfalfa cultures devoid of synthetic auxin and kinetin, a treatment that reduces RBR expression to almost undetectable levels (Dudits et al., 2011). However, it has not yet been investigated whether Ca^{2+} signaling is involved in these responses. A quiescence-associated change in the mitochondria shape, similar to that observed in animals, has been also reported in yeasts (Laporte et al., 2018), suggesting that the mechanisms of the proliferation-quiescence-based

functional block may have appeared in evolution even before living organisms developed multicellularity.

Thus, entrance in the quiescence state in animal cells depends on the activity of specific Ca^{2+} transporters. In plants, the role of Ca^{2+} in the induction of quiescence is still unclear, but it does not seem to be directly involved in this process.

The fuzziness of the quiescence concept does not allow establishing a strict relationship between this program and the proposed mutually exclusive chemotaxis-migration functional block of animal cells. Quiescent T-lymphocytes are able to migrate, but in the case of stem cells (which display quiescence among other properties), the less differentiated they are, the less are they prone to migration (*YP* — unpublished observations). This observation suggests that there is an additional interplay between programs within the proliferation-quiescence-based functional block, and this interplay evolved by the establishment of new links with the chemotaxis-migration functional block through differentiation. Failures in these pathways would be lethal at the early stages of embryonic development, although they will not necessarily be reflected in the viability of the corresponding isolated cell lines (see section 2.3.5.).

2.3.4. Apoptosis

Unlike other programs of the proliferation-quiescence-based functional block, apoptosis, upon mitochondrial outer membrane permeabilization (MOMP), is an irreversible process (Humeau et al., 2017). As apoptosis has death as a phenotype, in multicellular organisms it was proposed to have evolved in association with cell proliferation (Meikrantz and Schlegel, 1995). Indeed, apoptotic pathways in animals are activated mostly in proliferating cells (Alenzi, 2005), although its activation from the quiescent state has also been described (Meikrantz and Schlegel, 1995). Apoptotic pathways are regulated by several key players of the cell cycle machinery: the E2F1 transcription factor, whose apoptotic-inducing activity is restrained by interaction with Rb (Pucci et al., 2000), CDK1 (acting as a sensitizing factor), cyclins D1, D3 (TNF-induced) (Alenzi, 2005). Cyclin-mediated apoptosis also depends on additional signals, either promoting or arresting proliferation (Pucci et al., 2000).

In animals, apoptosis strongly depends on Ca^{2+} signaling and is initiated either by a long-term cytosolic Ca^{2+} overload through activation of CaN-proapoptotic BCL-2 family members (Dubois et al., 2016), or by a mitochondrial Ca^{2+} overload that takes place through the $\text{IP}_3\text{R-Grp75-VDAC1-MCU}$ interaction interfaces located within the ER-mitochondria mitochondria-associated membranes (MAMs) sites (Marchi et al., 2018). This second route induces piercing of the mitochondrial membrane by the proteins ‘Bcl-2 homologous antagonist killer’ (BAK) and ‘Bcl-2-associated X’ (BAX), which results in the release of the mitochondrial content into the cytosol (MOMP) (Edlich, 2018), and serves as the convergent point of apoptosis induction by either positive (specific activators) or

negative signals (like withdrawal of particular growth factors, e.g. IL-2/6 in mouse myeloma lines, or nerve growth factor in the case of sympathetic neurons; Meikrantz and Schlegel, 1995).

Normally, BAX coursing from the mitochondria to the cytosol and back prevents apoptosis (Edlich, 2018). This translocation depends on (and seemingly feeds back into) BCL-2-regulated IP₃Rs-mediated Ca²⁺ oscillations, similar to those induced by the oncogenes Bcl-XL and Mcl-1 that promote the widely-reported “pro-survival” Ca²⁺ oscillations (Humeau et al., 2017).

Apoptosis can be downregulated by treatment with miRNA against the mitochondrial Ca²⁺ uniporter MCU. On the other hand, MCU upregulation enhances metastasis (in a way independent from cell proliferation) (Paupe and Prudent, 2018). MCU affinity for Ca²⁺ is very low, and its activation requires high concentrations of this ion, which are established at MAMs (Paupe and Prudent, 2018). Thus, a mechanism can be proposed in which lysosomal TPCs (see section 2.2) and mitochondrial MCU compete for VDAC: mtROS released through VDACS promotes cell migration, while cytosolic Ca²⁺ increase induces VDAC-MCU tethering, resulting in migration inhibition, mitochondrial Ca²⁺ overload, and finally — apoptosis. In this way, competition for VDAC could serve as a mechanistical explanation for the mutual exclusivity of the migration and apoptosis programs.

In plants, programmed cell death (PCD) is regulated by two sets of genes, which activate this program in response to developmental (dPCD) or environmental (ePCD) stimuli (Locato and De Gara, 2018). Unlike in animals, the role of Ca²⁺ in PCD induction and execution is much less evident. Instead, both ePCD and dPCD are triggered by reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (ROS, RNS) and hormones (salicylic acid, ethylene, gibberellin) (Locato and De Gara, 2018), although the PCD-triggering capacity of ROS depends on the site and type of ROS involved (Reape et al., 2018).

Plants lack homologs of animal regulators of apoptosis, but curiously —and very similar to the situation with cADPR described in section 2.2.— the ectopic expression of animal homologs can induce or suppress programmed cell death in vegetal cells, presumably through conserved structural features of the involved proteins (Dickman et al., 2017; Reape et al., 2018). Moreover, there is emerging evidence that the central vacuole can play a role analogous to phagocytosis (Dickman et al., 2017), further suggesting that the plant vacuole can be involved in an “internal migration” mechanism (see section 2.2). Nevertheless, unlike in animals, programmed cell death in plants apparently does not compensate for cell number increase due to proliferation (hyperplasia). Thus, despite some structural conservation of the mechanisms regulating apoptosis in multicellular organisms, execution of this program and some of the signals triggering it evolved independently: in animals, apoptosis can be directly induced within proliferation sites and is very sensitive to the cells environment crowding (signals about which are transduced by members of the Ca²⁺

signaling toolkit), while programmed cell death in plants is a process relatively independent from neighbor cells.

2.3.5. Differentiation

In this section we refer to differentiation as a program belonging to the proliferation-quiescence functional block, although at least two differentiation modes can be distinguished (Gilbert, 2010): 1) autonomous and 2) conditional, suggesting that within this framework differentiation should not be considered a single program (this point will be further discussed in section 2.4.2.). Interestingly, studies on unicellular eukaryotes showed that generation of differentiated somatic cells in unicellular organisms is not an evolutionary stable strategy: such organisms cannot compete with non-differentiating unicellular organisms and are outcompeted by multicellular differentiating ones (Wahl and Murray, 2016).

Works on *Dictyostelium* showed that individual cell fate 1) depends on preexisting cell-to-cell differences in the cytosolic Ca^{2+} level, which in turn depends on the cell cycle stage at which starvation took place, and 2) is dynamically established through mutual cell-cell interactions (Saran et al., 1994). Interestingly, the pre-set differentiation program favors a positive outcome: fruiting bodies are formed even in absence of extracellular Ca^{2+} (Baskar et al., 2000), i.e. — in the worst natural (Ca^{2+} -related) scenario a mold can encounter.

Like in *Dictyostelium*, differentiation in animal cells proceeds at different cytosolic Ca^{2+} levels (as it happens during dorso-ventral patterning in *Drosophila*, McMillen et al., 2019), which are probably established as described in section 2.3.1. Nevertheless, examples analyzed at the beginning of section 2.3.2. suggest that attainment of the final differentiated state is linked to a generally lower cytosolic Ca^{2+} level than during proliferation, apparently in contradiction to results presented in section 2.1. on background Ca^{2+} dynamics. Both sets of results can be reconciled by proposing that —unlike in *Dictyostelium*— differentiation in animals requires proliferation. In other words, while (terminal) differentiation itself is linked to a lower cytosolic Ca^{2+} level, its attainment requires transition through high-cytosolic Ca^{2+} -associated proliferating states. Proliferation-dependent differentiation has been observed, for example, in T lymphocytes (see Viola et al., 2005), butterflies' wing scales, and *Caenorhabditis elegans* cells (Svetlov, 1978). Signaling pathways and transcription factors behind differentiation are mostly conserved in different tissues (Sagner and Briscoe, 2017), suggesting that the sensitivity of differentiation to modulation by external factors is what determines whether differentiation will proceed autonomously or in a conditional way. The relative autonomy of proliferation in specified regions (Svetlov, 1978; see section 2.4.2.) supports this view. Importantly, migration has also been proposed to be essential for differentiation, for example of neural progenitors (Horigane et al., 2019). It is possible that these cells have to migrate in order to find the appropriate physico-chemical environment in which differentiation can proceed further (see section 2.4.).

Thus, differentiation involves a rearrangement and/or succession/replacement of elements of the Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit. These observations further suggest the possibility that stem cells are able to preserve their stem identity by secluding “differentiation factor(s)” resulting from proliferation into their progeny which is committed to differentiation.

Mechanistically, cell fate commitment in animals takes place via $\text{IP}_3\text{Rs}-\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{CaN}$ -[specific NFAT] pathway, as determined in differentiating cardiomyocytes (Wang et al., 2017) and myocytes (Stiber et al., 2005). Interestingly, Ca^{2+} released through IP_3Rs induces NFAT nuclear *entry* in undifferentiated skeletal myoblasts, but in differentiated ones a similar stimulus provokes NFAT nuclear *exit*. Instead, in differentiated myotubes NFAT nuclear entry is induced by RYR-mediated Ca^{2+} transients. These responses were shown to depend on the scaffolding protein Homer, that interacts both with IP_3Rs and RYRs, and is expressed as a part of the myotubes’ differentiation program (Stiber et al., 2005). RYRs also mediate neuronal differentiation through functional coupling with L- but not N-, P-, or Q-type Ca_v1 Ca^{2+} channels (Resende et al., 2010). Overall, IP_3Rs emerge as a key factor linking multicellularity and differentiation in animals. If their activity is affected, it results in embryonic or larval lethality in multicellular organisms, and abolished cAMP/folic acid-stimulated Ca^{2+} entry and inability to aggregate (=“multicellularize”) in *Dictyostelium* (Traynor et al., 2000).

In plants, the balance between differentiation and proliferation is regulated by the auxin/cytokinin hormones ratio (Pierre-Jerome et al., 2018). Similar to *Dictyostelium*, the fate of vegetal cells can be determined by intrinsic factors, but this can be overridden by the cell’s position and external cues: for example, root induction depends on auxin, but shoot formation requires high cytokinin-to-auxin ratio (and this treatment is able to transform root primordia into growing shoots in just four days; Pierre-Jerome et al., 2018). Auxin and cytokinin’s roles are opposite in shoots and roots: in roots, auxin controls cell division, and cytokinin induces differentiation, while in shoots their roles are reversed (Pierre-Jerome et al., 2018). Nevertheless, whether cell proliferation in plants is required for differentiation, and how is hormonal signaling translated into transcriptional responses remains largely unknown.

Maintenance of the differentiated state is accomplished by positive feedback loops involving transcription factors, autocrine factors, or paracrine factors as described by Gilbert (2010), and *per se* seemingly does not require Ca^{2+} signaling. Modifications of Ca^{2+} signaling functional blocks are nevertheless involved in *changes* to the differentiation state. This is especially notable in the case of cancer (see section 2.4.3.).

A process closely related to differentiation is *dedifferentiation*, which corresponds to the reversion of the differentiated state to the stem state, and is proposed to constitute a step in the epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition (EMT) in animals (Wang and Unternaehrer, 2018). Similar to differentiation, dedifferentiation constitutes *a set* of programs, which

depends on the transcription factors involved, the cell types and the microenvironment of the cells (Zhang and Weinberg, 2018). Thus, generally speaking, EMT programs can differ among tissues of different type (Yang et al., 2020).

During an EMT-like process, cell detachment was shown to be accompanied by the rearrangement of cell-cell contact sites-associated Ca^{2+} signals (Okeke et al., 2016). Conversely, establishment of cell-cell contacts includes, as a step, the confinement of Ca^{2+} activity to specific narrow spaces involved in cell-cell interaction (Okeke et al., 2016). Thus, EMT activation probably involves a two-step mixed scenario, during which Ca^{2+} signaling is rapidly rearranged, followed by a slower process involving the turnover of already expressed proteins, and the expression of Ca^{2+} -related mesenchymal state markers. Such Ca^{2+} signaling modifications would constitute a missing step in the major changes proposed to take place during EMT (Yang et al., 2020). It is also possible that the dynamics of the two steps of Ca^{2+} signaling modifications differs in the M-to-E and E-to-M transitions, underlying their “spectrum-like” character (Yang et al., 2020). Of note, EMT activation in non-cancer stem cells is thought to convert them into cancer stem cells, and this process is presumably bidirectional (Zhang and Weinberg, 2018). Importantly, EMT is generally linked to increased cell migration (Liu et al., 2015), but it is also linked to stemness traits such as decreased proliferation, drug insensitivity and resistance to apoptosis (Kim et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2020). Nevertheless, it is currently unknown if these traits are regulated independently of EMT (Yang et al., 2020). In addition, it is currently unknown whether EMT engagement requires cell division, as suggested above for differentiation. In the case of differentiation, it is possible that, once the cell becomes *determined* (Gilbert, 2010), no further proliferation is required to attain the end fate. If EMT engagement does not require cell division, it could correspond to the cell entering into a “pre-determined” state, before the end-fate is attained. This issue is further discussed in section 2.4.4.

2.4 Ca^{2+} signaling in the multicellular environment

Since the first attempts to culture primary cells, it was noticed that they tend to *dedifferentiate* with the increase of the passage number (Coon, 1966). On the other hand, an opposite tendency to spontaneously *differentiate* is a well-known feature of pluripotent stem cells. This suggests that, generally speaking, cultured cells represent a living matter with adaptations developed to the particular conditions of growth in culture. Following our proposal, Ca^{2+} signaling remodeling plays a crucial role in the development of such adaptations, which become reflected in what appears to us as the phenotype of the cultured cells. This phenomenon can also be appreciated not only at the cellular level, but also at the organismal level, as suggested by experiments with intragenerational planaria adaptation to culture media composition change (Emmons-Bell et al., 2019).

At this —supracellular or tissular— scale, the number of possible inputs (both internal and external stimuli) dramatically increases, and the same holds true for the potential responses

of the Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit elements. An attempt to categorize the response types produced by all imaginable inputs turns into a technically extremely challenging and demanding task. Even if the required subcellular Ca^{2+} transient tracking is achieved in multicellular structures, a link between them and the subsequently-arising changes can be established only in the form of correlations, limiting our possibilities to clearly assign direct outcomes to particular features of Ca^{2+} signaling taking place during morphogenesis. We propose that Ca^{2+} signaling is individually and dynamically established in a conditioned manner. Thus, the question here should rather be *how is species-dependent Ca^{2+} signaling consistency preserved between generations*, despite its dynamic nature. It seems reasonable to think that *the consistency of the cellular environment* is the major factor responsible for the stability and reproducibility of the Ca^{2+} signaling features in living organisms. An example supporting this statement can be the canine transmissible venereal tumor (CTVT) — *de facto*, a vertebrate-derived parasitic cell culture, that, despite genetic rearrangements, retrotransposon insertions, the loss of 646 genes, more than 10,000 genes with non-synonymous variants, and ~500 years-long dispersal across continents, displays (unlike laboratory-cultured cell lines) a remarkable stability and lack of subclonal heterogeneity (Murchison et al., 2014). Conversely, particular dog breeds, most of which were created through numerous genetic bottlenecks, display higher susceptibility (=appropriate mutations and favorable environments for their expression) to develop particular cancer types (Nunney et al., 2015).

In other words, *development itself* seems to act as an instructive and deterministic factor in the establishment of the appropriate Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit pertaining to a particular organism. Ca^{2+} signaling acts in a way conceptually similar to that proposed by Alexander G. Gurwitsch (1874-1954) in his “morphogenetic field” theory (1912-1944). The viability of an organism as a particular “configuration” of Ca^{2+} signaling in a given environment, and the organism’s ability to generate progeny, underlie the preservation and reproduction of such configuration from one generation to another.

Thus, enumerating all the possible input-output relationships is not the most effective approach in studying Ca^{2+} signaling establishment and remodeling by the cellular environment. We can, nevertheless, identify three key means, or factors, that become restraining/instructive at this, tissular, level of organization. Amongst such commonly-accepted means by which cells mutually influence each other within an organism, guiding differentiation, are (after fundamental theoretical and experimental works by Hans Spemann (1869-1941), Dmitrii P. Filatov (1876-1943), Ivan I. Schmalhausen (1884-1963), Pavel G. Svetlov (1892-1974), Rudolf Raff (1941-2019), and several contemporary researchers): 1) mechanical cues, and signals of 2) chemical (molecular-genetic) and 3) electrical nature, all of them important for growth and maintenance of the different organism parts integrated into a single unified system (see Newman, 2019; Pietak et al., 2019). Together they constitute the main cell-cell interaction means.

Apart from approaching cell-cell interactions by analyzing the means through which cells influence each other, interactions can be studied from the viewpoint of the supracellular phenomena they underlie. Such phenomena are *development* (either normal or aberrant, e.g., *cancer*), and *regeneration*, all of them involving the cell-cell interaction modalities enunciated above.

2.4.1. Cell-cell interaction (differentiating/specifying) means

Being originated through cell-cell interactions, differentiating/specifying means serve as guides for organized modification of cells ensembles in multicellular organisms, transforming individual cell cycles into the development of an integral multicellular organism. As these factors are intimately linked to Ca^{2+} signaling, we propose that they determine how will the organism's Ca^{2+} signaling (and the processes it regulates) be topologically distributed in tissues during a particular stage of development. Further (Ca^{2+} signaling-established) development gives start to subsequent changes in Ca^{2+} signaling — as an emergent feature, and in such non-direct way this pathway participates in the organism's morphogenesis. Thus, by initiating differentiation, Ca^{2+} signaling —through the differentiation/specification means— drives tissue specification, which in turn promotes further differentiation of the cells composing it, by remodeling their Ca^{2+} signaling.

A recent evidence of this particular role of Ca^{2+} signaling in morphogenesis is the participation of RYRs —apart from their “traditional” role in the excitation-contraction coupling in muscles— in the localization of the Sonic Hedgehog (Sh) activity (Shaw et al., 2018). Similar roles for Ca^{2+} were identified previously without establishing the exact identity of the Ca^{2+} transporters responsible for the morphogenetic outcome (e.g., Hibino et al., 2006). This view also coincides well with the role Ca^{2+} signaling has in cancer progression (changes in Ca^{2+} signaling are not cancer-driver mutations themselves *per se*, but their acquisition can influence further cancer evolution; Hoth et al., 2016), and the more general observation that in eukaryotes the Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit expanded at rates higher than other functions, “and with an increased rate of diversification that coincides with prior hypotheses of increasing organismal complexity as measured by cell type diversity” (Marchadier et al., 2016). We can nevertheless state that the feedback pathway from the tissular/organismal level down to the cellular one is probably the less explored aspect of Ca^{2+} signaling in whole organisms.

It should be noted that, apart from these means, which directly arise from cell-cell interactions, morphogenesis can also be influenced by a plethora of other biotic and abiotic factors (Tung and Levin, 2020). In addition, some of the elements of the Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit that participate in the establishment of cell-cell interactions in multicellular organism have homologues in unicellular eukaryotes (Plattner and Verkhatsky, 2018). Although the analysis of the changes that accompanied the transition from unicellularity to multicellularity constitutes an interesting research subject, this issue will not be approached in the present work.

2.4.1.1. Mechanical signals

Mechanical forces act across scales, regulating cell proliferation, migration and differentiation, but also providing feedback about tissues' size and shape, both during development and in adult life, and not only in animals but also in plants (Mammoto and Ingber, 2010; Eder et al., 2017; Ferreira and Vermot, 2017; Landrein and Ingram, 2019). Moreover, mechanical stresses are able to activate (without fertilization) *Drosophila* and sea urchin eggs, and are known to induce a rapid pluripotency loss in undifferentiated embryonic stem cells (Mammoto and Ingber, 2010).

With few exceptions, mechanical stimuli, calcium signals linked to them, and transporters generating them, as well as the molecular mechanisms involved in mechanosensation and mechanotransduction, are all studied separately. In these conditions, determining how the different mechanical stimuli are converted into physiological responses turns into a challenging task which can be attempted to reconstruct from results obtained in different studies.

Roughly, cells can be viewed as structures in a prestressed (tensegrity) state which can be subjected to mechanical stimuli either from the extracellular space (gravity, pressure, touch, shear stress, pulling, etc.), or from the cell interior (turgor, traction forces developed by the cell itself). Different static load ranges, as well as their ranges of change (dynamic loads) are apparently linked to different configurations of mechanosensation and mechanotransduction mechanisms, at least in animals. In addition, cells' responses to mechanical stimuli can vary depending on whether they are interconnected in tissues or not.

During development, these mechanical stimuli and transduction mechanisms can affect morphogenesis by inducing polarization, and in animals — additionally by inducing cell migration (Svetlov, 1978 and section 2.2.1.). For example, high confinement and low adhesion conditions are known to induce a migratory phenotype in cells of a large number of tissue types (Brunet and Arendt, 2016 and section 2.2.2.), suggesting a mechanism of morphogenesis depending on durotaxis-guided migrations. During development, neural crest EMT and migration onset are seemingly induced by a stiffness increase in the adjacent mesoderm (Yamada and Sixt, 2019). Similarly, mechanical properties of solid tumors have been shown to promote characteristic hallmarks of cancer — invasion and metastasis (Canales et al., 2019). In animals, cell shape itself and the cytoskeletal structure can be defined by the cell prestress level, by the corresponding properties of the extracellular matrix, by the strength of the cell's adhesion to other cells or the extracellular matrix, or by the number/size of cells within the tissue. These parameters influence not only cells' morphology, but also their fate (Mammoto and Ingber, 2010).

It is currently thought that during normal development mechanical interactions between cells allow them to compare their growth rate with that of surrounding companions, so that differences are smoothed out, resulting in a uniform tissular growth (Eder et al., 2017). For

example, the balance between hyperplasia induced by administration of mitogens, and apoptosis induced by their withdrawal (Meikrantz and Schlegel, 1995), has been shown to depend on the transcription factor Myc (Sarosiek et al., 2017), whose proapoptotic effect is “pre-set” but normally suppressed (Pucci et al., 2000). The Myc-dependent apoptotic pathway is downregulated by (the “prosurvival” proto-oncogene) Bcl-2, which reduces ER Ca^{2+} content by decreasing the activity and expression levels of SERCAs, and increasing the leak of this ion through InsP_3Rs , thus impinging on ER-mitochondria Ca^{2+} transfer (Bittremieux et al., 2016; Humeau et al., 2017). Conversely, apoptosis is promoted by p53 under cell stress through mitochondrial Ca^{2+} overload, by p53 recruitment to the ER and ER-mitochondria MAMs, and its activating effect on SERCA (Bittremieux and Bultynck, 2015). In this way, the balance between Myc and p53 activities apparently establishes the cells’ mechanosensitivity thresholds, and underlies the different outcomes of compression imposed on tumors (and possibly — on tissues during development): either metastasis/migration (Canales et al., 2019), or proliferation arrest and apoptosis (Eder et al., 2017). An indirect evidence for such a role of Myc is the “cell competition” phenomenon: higher Myc levels confer cells a “supercompetitor” phenotype, able to displace “weaker” cells with lower Myc levels from the same tissue by inducing their apoptosis. Outcompetition is abolished by reduction of p53 levels in supercompetitor cells (de la Cova et al., 2014), suggesting a possible mechanism of cell survival in hyperplastic (compressed) tissues, and of apoptosis induction upon mitogens withdrawal. Of note, p53 expression is downregulated by NF- κ B activation induced by cytosolic Ca^{2+} increase (Lee et al., 2018). Mechanical cues are also integrated with mitogenic ones through YAP — a transcription factor that, together with Myc, controls cell growth and organ size in response to changes in cell adhesion, apico-basal polarity, cytoskeletal tension, and mitogens (Crocì et al., 2017).

During optical cup development, mechanical strain resulting from cell proliferation was shown to induce neural retina (NR) invagination through polarization of actin distribution in cells at the site. This process is facilitated by the lateral (apico-basal) constriction of cells at the joint region between the invagination and the cup itself (the so-called neural retina-retinal pigment epithelium, NR-RPE, boundary), which is accompanied by intracellular Ca^{2+} spikes (Okuda et al., 2018a). Similar Ca^{2+} oscillations remodel the actin cytoskeleton through the small GTPases RhoA and Rac1 (Paupe and Prudent, 2018, see also section 2.2.2.), which in cultured cells regulate the formation of stress fibers and focal adhesions (RhoA), and of the branched network of actin filaments in lamellipodia (Rac1) (Canales et al., 2019). The Ca^{2+} transients that activate Rho GTPases are typically produced by the activity of TRP channels (Canales et al., 2019).

Actomyosin contractility is also proposed as the primary mechanism delimiting compartment boundaries in developing embryos. In the developing *Drosophila* wing, boundaries are maintained by tension exerted on cell-cell contacts by myosin II, regulated by the Rho/ROCK pathway. In turn, Rho/ROCK are regulated by the Wnt/PCP pathway, as

it was shown in *Xenopus* and *Danio* (Mammoto and Ingber, 2010). Cytoskeletal tension regulates Wnt/PCP signaling, which controls cell junctions, and is critical for the establishment of cell orientation (Mammoto and Ingber, 2010).

An important mechanism of Ca^{2+} supply in different mechanical conditions are the transient receptor channels (TRPs). The different gating properties of members of this channel family allow them to activate under different stimuli types and ranges. The particular functions of some of these channels are presented below. TRPC5 activates Rac1, promoting a migratory phenotype by suppressing the formation of stress fibers and focal adhesions. Of note, activation of Rac1 by growth factors induces TRPC5 translocation to the plasma membrane, where it regulates motility and morphology, as it was shown in growth cones of hippocampal neurons. Conversely, activation of RhoA by TRPC6 in different contexts promotes the formation of stress fibers and adhesion, conferring the cell high contractility and low motility. Another member of this channel family, TRPV4, is present in cells experiencing a relatively constant range of load, but absent in those whose range of load tends to fluctuate (Canales et al., 2019). Another TRP, Trpp2 (PKD2), was shown to participate in left-right specification in vertebrates, although the Ca^{2+} flux required for this process is apparently generated through interactions with TRPV4, PKD1 or PKD111. Interestingly, PKD1 can be activated by a morphogen of the Wnt family (see section 2.4.1.2.) to induce Ca^{2+} transients. In addition, the Trpp2/PKD1 complex apparently has signaling properties not related to its mechanosensitivity-related ion channel function (Ferreira and Vermot, 2017).

In tissues, tension forces (stretching), which depend on the substrate stiffness among other factors, control cell division rate and, through cadherin, align the mitotic spindle orientation to the cell shape at tricellular junctions (Mammoto and Ingber, 2010; Eder et al., 2017; Nestor-Bergmann et al., 2019). In epithelial cells, adhesion to the extracellular matrix through integrin-containing focal adhesions plays a similar role (Eder et al., 2017). Additionally, asymmetric cell-cell contacts, stabilized by N-cadherine, are important for symmetry breaking in species in which this process does not rely on flow mediated by cilia, depending instead on cell migration (Ferreira and Vermot, 2017). Interestingly, the connection state of the cell may affect its Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit: in pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) cells' IP_3Rs are juxtaposed with tight junctions, but upon cells detachment IP_3Rs rapidly translocate to their leading edges, surrounding focal adhesions that regulate paxillin aggregation at these locations (Okeke et al., 2016).

In plants, pre-stressed transvacuolar strands and the phragmosome determine the division plane and growth constraints (one of which is the minimization of the resulting daughter cells areas; Dumais, 2007). This process, and the directional cell expansion, are regulated by microtubule arrays, although apparently not in a direct way: plant cells can maintain their form for hours after microtubules have been depolymerized, and the forces they exert are extremely small compared to the stiffness values of the cell walls (Takeuchi et al.,

2016; Hamant et al., 2019). Instead, microtubules align in the direction of maximal stress and guide the deposition of cellulose microfibrils by the cellulose synthase complexes, although in some cases the cell shape itself acts as a microtubule orienting factor; the resulting cellulose patterns are proposed to define the new tensile patterns that will maintain the microtubule array orientation during further growth (Hamant et al., 2019; Kierzkowski and Routier-Kierzkowska, 2019; Landrein and Ingram, 2019). This system appears to be highly autonomous, as depolymerization of the actin cytoskeleton does not visibly alter the microtubules array. Conversely, the microtubule cytoskeleton is required to organize the actin cytoskeleton (Durand-Smet et al., 2019). Ca^{2+} has little effect on microtubules, and destabilization of microtubules by Ca^{2+} is apparently mediated by other proteins (Qin et al., 2012). Another proposed mechanism of growth regulation involves auxin PIN1 transporters, whose polarized distribution can be affected by mechanical stresses (Landrein and Ingram, 2019).

Plants also possess mechanosensitive channels, although little is known about their identity and their participation in plant morphogenesis. Among the most studied ones are plasma membrane-localized Ca^{2+} -permeable Mid1-Complementing Activity (MCA) channels, that were shown to be involved in the roots' ability to penetrate the substrate, and in the perception of developmentally-imposed mechanical signals (Basu and Haswell, 2018). Other examples of Ca^{2+} -permeable mechanosensitive channels are *DEFECTIVE KERNEL1* (DEK1), which is vitally important for maintaining cell-cell adhesion under tension, and *REDUCED HYPEROSMOLARITY-INDUCED [Ca^{2+}]_i INCREASE 1* (OSCA1), which participates in the response to hyperosmotic stress (Landrein and Ingram, 2019). It is worth mentioning that most of the original works present these examples in plants considering Ca^{2+} signaling as a mere stimuli-transducing agent, as specified in the Introduction.

2.4.1.2. Chemical signals

Chemical signals as differentiating means are the most variable — they define the chemical landscape within which the living form will evolve, including the metabolism type, nutrition, growth regulation, and chemical signals that will provide the basis for the cells' ability to make decisions (and thus, broadly speaking — the organism's ecological niche). For example, most multicellular living forms we know rely on oxygen for their subsistence, although there are exceptions even to this common rule: members of the *Loricifera* phylum permanently live in anoxic conditions (Danovaro et al., 2010). Experiments with starvation suggest an additional layer of regulation by nutrients' availability: several organisms respond to starvation first by reducing the number of cells composing their tissues, and then — by degeneration (Svetlov, 1978), probably through autophagy mediated by TOR inhibition (Faris et al., 2019).

Yet, cell-cell differentiating interactions through chemical signals generally refer to fate specification in animals, induced through morphogens (Gilbert, 2010). Morphogens are a small set of released soluble proteins belonging to FGF, Hh, and Wnt families, and the

TGF- β superfamily (includes the TGF- β family, activin, BMPs, Nods, Vg1, etc.), whose relatives can be found even in unicellular eukaryotes (Gilbert, 2010; Sagner and Briscoe, 2017; Fields et al., 2020). Their ability to specify different tissue fates during multicellular organism development has been proposed to result from several rounds of sequential induction, gradients' interaction and differential interpretation by target cells, and to depend not only on a particular morphogen concentration, but also on its concentration dynamics and signaling duration (Sagner and Briscoe, 2017). A theoretical analysis of patterns arising from morphogen' gradients interaction was for the first time provided in the highly cited work by Alan Turing (we will not be an exception, Turing, 1952), long before morphogens were actually discovered.

The roles of particular morphogens during development are detailed elsewhere (Tabata and Takei, 2004; Gilbert, 2010; Sagner and Briscoe, 2017; Huizar et al., 2019; Fields et al., 2020), and will be skipped in the present work. Interestingly, in plants, the effect of phytohormones has been likened to that of the morphogens in animals: although some hormones exert a long-distance action, most of them act like paracrine factors and evoke context-dependent responses (Besnard et al., 2011).

Although in distant lineages related morphogens can exert different functions (Fields et al., 2020), within a single organism the same morphogen can participate in the specification of different tissue types (Gilbert, 2010). Specificity during this process is accomplished by particular gene expression profiles in the receiving cells, and by differential sensitivity to the inducing signal. In a sort of emergent-like response, a perceived signal induces changes in the genes expressed, which results in a new cell state, and defines (restricts) further its possible differentiation routes (Sagner and Briscoe, 2017). A specific cell fate, thus, is determined by “competency windows” which depend on the duration and order of morphogens' action, and the context in which they act (Sagner and Briscoe, 2017). Importantly, morphogens act in the timescale of minutes to few hours, whereas the resulting tissue pattern usually takes hours to days to form (Sagner and Briscoe, 2017). Moreover, patterning takes place during phases of active growth, thus an open question in the field of “pure” chemically-induced morphogenesis is how are morphogen gradients dynamically scaled to fit up with the growing structures' size (Sagner and Briscoe, 2017; Garric and Bakers, 2018).

Despite the proposed leading role of reaction-diffusion mechanisms in tissue patterning, the small number of available morphogens suggests the participation of other factors to produce the existing tissue diversity (Sagner and Briscoe, 2017). Additionally, contradictions to the activator-inhibitor model — one of the central concepts of the Turing's model, and other limitations to the interaction of morphogens' gradients as the sole mechanism of morphogenesis, have been observed. For instance (after Mercker et al., 2013; Brinkmann et al., 2018; Pietak et al., 2019):

- 1) in most cases the postulated long-range inhibitor cannot be identified;
- 2) achieving steady-state concentration gradients in growing and shape-changing structures is difficult and requires long time (in the order of weeks even in ~1 cm-long flatworms [used as a model object to study morphogenesis and regeneration], while in reality this process takes 72 hours or less);
- 3) it is impossible to use a same model gradient to describe the 1-headed or experimentally-obtained 2-headed flatworms (see section 2.4.4.);
- 4) unrealistic gradients emerge in certain structures, as gradients are proposed to form with respect to the longest length of the modeled object.

Moreover, pure Turing's mechanisms are not supported in cases when patterns form in a self-organized way from dissociated and re-aggregated cells (Brinkmann et al., 2018) — a result that has nevertheless been experimentally observed.

It has to be pointed out, that the way in which morphogen gradients are established *in vivo* is not entirely understood. Several mechanisms of morphogens spreading have been observed, e.g. — facilitated diffusion, shuttling, etc., that can occur either in the extracellular space, or through the cell cytosol (Huizar et al., 2019). Thus, form establishment through interaction of reaction-diffusion mechanisms with the other differentiation means has also been proposed, and in some cases observed. For example, in regenerating fragments of the flatworm *Dugesia japonica*, neurons net polarity determines the Hh directional (“vector”) transport, required to establish the antero-posterior polarity. Gradients generated through this mechanism self assemble and are virtually scale-independent (Pietak et al., 2019). In another example, *Drosophila* Dpp release and uptake were shown to rely on exo- and endocytosis processes similar to those involved in neurotransmitter transport, displaying a marked coupling to cytosolic Ca^{2+} concentration (Huizar et al., 2019). From this observation, it was proposed that cytosolic Ca^{2+} level can act as a modulator of morphogens' transport. Ca^{2+} signaling (its spike frequency) has also been proposed to encode Shh concentration, which is required for correct neuronal differentiation (Huizar et al., 2019).

Apart from the neural system-assisted mechanism of establishment of morphogens' gradients, the influence of mechanical stimuli on morphogens distribution and action has been observed and studied through mathematical models. This approach postulates that morphogens patterns change mechanical properties of cells and tissues, which, after a physical change, back-modulate morphogens patterns (Mammoto and Ingber, 2010; Mercker et al., 2013; Brinkmann et al., 2018). Several models exploring such mechano-chemical coupling have been presented to date. Among their most notable properties are a low sensitivity to perturbations of initial conditions (robustness; even if a single morphogen is considered in the model), a fast and long range of action (making unnecessary the

Turing's inhibitor gradient), dynamic and complex topologies are directly involved in pattern formation (for instance, different types of undulation, tubulations and branching easily result from even linear relationships between chemical and mechanical cues) (Mercker et al., 2013; Brinkmann et al., 2018; Okuda et al., 2018b). These models are based on known effects of morphogens on the actin and microtubule cytoskeletons. For example, the Wnt pathway regulates the myosin light chain phosphorylation state, the Hh pathway can activate Rho, ROCK and myosin II, affecting in this way the actin network contractility (Mammoto and Ingber, 2010).

Morphogens have been shown to delimit regions of Ca^{2+} signaling action. For example, Shh together with the signaling molecule-transcription factor β -catenin participate in the establishment of the gap junctional network, which restricts zones of Ca^{2+} signaling involved in feather morphogenesis in chicks (Huizar et al., 2019). In plants, Ca^{2+} signals were also shown to be involved in the polarized transport of PIN-FORMED1 (PIN1) (Li et al., 2019) — the transporter of auxin, the hormone that participates in plant organ formation and phyllotaxis (organ spacing) (Besnard et al., 2011). Interestingly, the turnover of this transporter at the plasma membrane was shown to be regulated by the auxin sensor ABP1, which, as mentioned previously, is involved in the regulation of vegetal cells proliferation (section 2.3.2., Besnard et al., 2011).

2.4.1.3. Electrical signals

At the tissular level, bioelectricity can be regarded to as the compound electric field generated by the differences in the electric potential across the plasma membrane of individual cells (Whited and Levin, 2019). Thus, the effect of bioelectricity is slow and does not require the cells generating it to be excitable. In this regard, bioelectricity is recognized as one of the cell-cell interaction means, which together with “chemical gradients” (section 2.4.1.2.) and “physical forces” (section 2.4.1.1.) regulates “developmental boundaries, gene expression, and organ size and identity” (Whited and Levin, 2019).

Bioelectric fields can produce Turing-like patterns without involving changes in genes expression or chemical morphogens (Brodsky and Levin, 2018). This process is largely dependent on intercellular gap junctions gating, which regulate cell-cell electrical coupling, favoring the regionalization of the electric potential and signal synchronization within the established regions (Cervera et al., 2019). Within such regions, the membrane potential appears to be persistently ‘set’ by the joint action of voltage-gated Ca^{2+} and Ca^{2+} -modulated K^+ channels (McMillen et al., 2019; Atsuta et al., 2019). Moreover, regions can change their potential, and thus — induce a switch between different programs or functional blocks (Whited and Levin, 2019). Physiological outcomes of such electrical polarization are already observable in organisms like budding yeast (Whited and Levin, 2019). In mice, limb mesenchyme was shown to switch its state from hyperpolarized undifferentiated (and

apparently — promoting proliferation) to depolarized during chondrocyte differentiation (Atsuta et al., 2019).

Despite Ca^{2+} being a charged species, the interaction between Ca^{2+} signaling and electrical fields is not straightforward. First, both depolarization and hyperpolarization events can induce a cytosolic Ca^{2+} increase, which fades as development advances, and correlates with migration of high- Ca^{2+} cells away from these zones during early stages of embryonic development. Interestingly, cell migration can be artificially enhanced by hyperpolarization of such zones, by overexpression of K^+ channels (McMillen et al., 2019). According to these authors, the internal Ca^{2+} dynamics may let individual cells know that their membrane potential is in accordance with the stage of development (manifesting as Ca^{2+} flashes), or is incorrectly set (inducing in this case a static Ca^{2+} increase, which disappears as cells depolarize/engage in differentiation, i.e., proceed to further development).

Ca^{2+} transients have also been proposed to serve (in addition to mechanical cues; see section 2.4.4.1.) as a readout of the organ size (Brodskiy et al., 2019). Using the *Drosophila* larval wing disc as a model of organogenesis, 4 qualitative classes of Ca^{2+} transients were identified, evoked in a concentration-dependent manner by a *Gaq/PLC* agonist: 1) single-cell Ca^{2+} spikes, 2) short-distance intercellular Ca^{2+} transients, 3) oscillatory long-range intercellular Ca^{2+} waves, and 4) increased cytosolic Ca^{2+} levels displaying low amplitude oscillations (“fluttering”). In all wings examined, the posterior compartment displayed a higher time-averaged amplitude of Ca^{2+} signals than the anterior one (correlating with growth rate differences in these compartments), and this difference was more evident in larger wing disks (Brodskiy et al., 2019). A more detailed analysis showed that this gradient was upstream-regulated by the morphogens *Hh* and *Dpp*, as perturbation of their signaling cascades abolished the antero-posterior Ca^{2+} signaling pattern, increasing the Ca^{2+} transients’ frequency across the full disc (Brodskiy et al., 2019). Interestingly, an increased Ca^{2+} spike activity in individual cells across the tissue can also result from the disruption of gap junctions, which simultaneously hampers the cell-cell Ca^{2+} signal propagation (i.e. — reduces the proportion of Ca^{2+} signals of classes 3 and 4).

Phenotypically, this results in smaller wings with affected or lost crossveins — an effect which is phenocopied by IP_3Rs knock down (Brodskiy et al., 2019). In addition to the spatial heterogeneity of Ca^{2+} signals, the same authors found that organ’s size increase during development was accompanied by a shift in the Ca^{2+} activity pattern from fluttering disc - to oscillatory waves - to stochastic spikes, at the end of larval development. Taken together, these results allowed the authors to experimentally confirm that development is accompanied by a reduction in the permeability of gap junctions, and regionalization, which is reflected in the succession of Ca^{2+} signaling patterns. Dynamic Ca^{2+} signals are also observed during differentiation of other tissue types (e.g., nervous, kidney, face; McMillen et al., 2019), suggesting the possibility that the same mechanism takes place during their morphogeneses. In conclusion, bioelectric regionalization is required for

demarcation of gene expression domains (Whited and Levin, 2019), and Ca^{2+} is proposed to close the feedback loop by regulating morphogen distribution (Brodskiy et al., 2019; Huizar et al., 2019).

Electric fields can also induce cellular migration and impart directionality to this movement, which in human keratinocytes was shown to depend on extracellular pH and GPCRs (Whited and Levin, 2019). Curiously, a similar electrotaxis pH-dependence mediated by changes in the membrane potential was reported for *Dictyostelium discoideum* cells (Gao et al., 2011). Moreover, membrane potential differences correlate with motility of the *Dictyostelium* cell types, seemingly underlying the “differentiation” — the cell sorting, that takes place within the slug (Kitami, 1988). Considering these results together with those presented in section 2.2, it would be interesting to analyze the possibility that, in addition to a pure chemical, cAMP-dependent mechanism of chemotaxis, *Dictyostelium* cells also orient themselves using a “ Ca^{2+} - + electro-taxis” mechanism.

Within delimited —and apparently depolarized regions— voltage-gated Ca^{2+} influx regulates differentiation. For example, Atsuta and coworkers (2019) found that during the earliest stages of chondrogenesis the activity of L-type VGCC $\text{Ca}_v1.2$ is essential for the expression of genes driving differentiation in developing limbs, and this process is mediated by the Ca^{2+} -dependent transcription factor NFATc1. Interestingly, other mutations leading to increased intracellular Ca^{2+} concentration in limbs did not result in aberrant chondrogenesis. Moreover, such increase promoted $\text{Ca}_v1.2$ -independent chondrocyte *proliferation*, suggesting the importance of the bioelectric field potential in triggering specific functional block programs. In addition, relevant to the subject of our work, $\text{Ca}_v1.2$ channels appear to have an “active window time” when they can influence differentiation, as their inhibition at posterior stages of development results only in modest differentiation defects. It was suggested that at these later stages the activity of other Ca^{2+} channels becomes important for further development (e.g., $\text{Ca}_v3.2$, TRPM7; Atsuta et al., 2019).

In addition to the tissular field potential, the nervous system has been proposed as an “advanced” mechanism of patterning, which is able both to control tissue polarity, and to remodel itself in accordance with anatomical changes taking place in the developing organism (Bischof et al., 2019). Through neuromediators, the neural system can regulate stem cell proliferation (Davis and Dailey, 2018) and innervate transplanted grafts in a voltage-dependent manner (Whited and Levin, 2019). At later stages of development, transfer of a peripheral nerve results in the modification of the new target muscle, the structure of which starts resembling the originally-innervated one’s (Bergmeister et al., 2019). These and other observations made in tumors and in developing or regenerating tissues, allowed Fields and collaborators (2020) to propose a broad active role of the nervous system in coordinating animal morphogenesis.

Bioelectrical fields are also important as differentiation means in plants. These fields were shown to result from pH differences between plant parts, and to be independent from the so-called “streaming potential” associated with polarized transport (Love et al., 2008). Similar to what has been observed in animals, these fields serve as prepatterning for future morphogenetic events by coordinating proliferation and organogenesis in depolarized zones, with their sign reversion or elimination inhibiting or completely arresting plant development (Carmen, 2008). The pH-dependence of the plant electric fields may reflect the importance of the PM P-type H^+ -ATPase as the main electrogenic source in vegetal cells, and as a driver of the plant “acid growth” — a proposed mechanism through which vegetal cells confined to cell walls can grow (Arsuffi and Braybrook, 2018). Interestingly, plants may also have a K^+ channel involved in “patterning” — GORK, which, due to its regulation by GABA, G-proteins, ATP, inositol, and protein phosphatases has been proposed as a master regulator of plant metabolism (Adem et al., 2019). However, to the best of our knowledge, the physiology of this channel has not yet been analyzed from the viewpoint of morphogenesis during development.

Like animals, plants also display propagating electrical signals. Currently, these signals are believed to carry out a sort of “stress notification” function, turning on defense mechanisms, enhancing plant resistance to stresses, and in some cases — transiently affecting growth (Sukhov et al., 2019), although they have no attributed effect on morphogenesis. Interestingly, their generation in plants has been associated with a transient inactivation of the PM H^+ -ATPase by cytosolic Ca^{2+} increase (Vodenev et al., 2006). From this observation, it has been suggested that propagating electrical signals in plants may transiently arrest growth (Sukhov et al., 2019). We expanded this view, proposing that the propagation of these signals along plant ramifications can, in a process resembling animal EMT (Wang and Unternaehrer, 2019), modulate morphogenetic processes when the environmental conditions a plant is “accustomed to” suddenly change. Through these signals, the plant senses changes in its “environmental norm” and turns on the corresponding mechanisms of adaptation, that allow a coordinated response from the different plant parts (Pérez Koldenkova and Hatsugai, 2018). Biphasic Ca^{2+} transients can be induced as a part of such responses to stresses, in some cases being the second phase responsible for the activation of adaptation mechanisms (Rudd and Franklin-Tong, 2001).

An interesting observation made in plants is the compensatory reciprocity of the Ca^{2+} signaling generation mechanisms in different representatives: some plants expanded their Ca^{2+} *influx* mechanisms at the expense of the *efflux* ones, while other plants display an opposite distribution (Marchadier et al., 2016). Of note, plants can also display propagating hyperpolarization signals (“system potentials”, Sukhov et al., 2019), however, it is currently unknown if both these phenomena are somehow related. Another question which needs solution is how does the acid growth mechanism work in underground plant parts: in these zones auxin, which has been proposed to mediate the acid-dependent cell expansion in

aerial plant parts, acts as an inhibitor of growth (Arsuffi and Braybrook, 2018). These questions may indicate the existence in plants of heretofore unexplored mechanisms of morphogenesis regulation by bioelectrical signaling which are specific to these organisms.

Electrical signals, like mechanical cues, can also act through the cell cytoskeleton. It is known that action potentials both in plants and animals can transiently arrest the actin-driven cytoplasmic streaming through F-actin fragmentation. In *Mimosa pudica* leaves movement is inhibited by treatments either over-stabilizing or depolymerizing F-actin (Baluška and Mancuso, 2019). The mechanism responsible for this effect is currently unknown, although it may be related to the reported electro-conductive properties of actin filaments, which underlie the so-called electroosmotic signaling (Lin and Cantiello, 1993; Cantiello and Prat, 1996).

2.4.2. Interaction of differentiating/specificating means and Ca^{2+} signaling during development. Establishment of specific Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit configurations

In developmental biology, the four principles of Karl Ernst von Baer establish a phylogenetic relationship between ontogeneses of animal species (cited from Gilbert, 2010): 1) the general features of a large group of animals appear earlier in development than do the specialized features of a smaller group; 2) less general characters develop from the more general, until finally the most specialized appear; 3) the embryo of a given species, instead of passing through the adult stages of lower animals, departs more and more from them; 4) therefore the early embryo of a higher animal is never like a lower animal, but only like its early embryo. These laws reflect the evolution of the interactions between inducing and reacting tissues, and the requirement of more ancient interactions for the evolutionary younger ones to occur during development (Schmalhausen, 1982). These principles and results described in previous sections suggest that in animals a key role in specification belongs to the position of the forming organ, which subsequently defines its identity. Grafting experiments confirm this suggestion, detailing it further: a resulting fate depends not only on the localization within an embryo, but also on the reactive tissue and the inducer, reflecting a “strength balance” between them (Svetlov, 1978). This mutual specificating influence of organs during development was analyzed in the work of Hans Spemann (1896-1941) and Dmitrii P. Filatov (1876-1943).

In plants, the overall relationship between individual organs and the whole organism appears to be less strict than in animals, i.e., plants display a higher degree of mosaicity than animals. Nevertheless, it appears that in plants the identity of the forming organ has higher relevance than its position, as it has been noticed in calli cultures, in which the differentiation pathway and generation of specific organs is controlled by hormonal supply (Carmen, 2008).

At the level of individuals, it can be said that development in particular animal species converge on a much more restricted set of possible phenotypic variants, compared to plants. These are fundamentally different strategies of morphogenesis in these two kingdoms.

Together, these observations pose the general question on the driving forces of development and evolution of development. Why do some organisms display more flexible shapes than others? Why do animals display more consistent forms than plants do? What properties of their development are responsible for this difference?

It has been previously noted that in the course of evolution, morphogenesis has changed toward a reduction of the influence of external factors over the developmental process, making it more independent (Schmalhausen, 1949). In contrast with the proposed “target morphology” concept (Fields et al., 2020), organisms’ shapes form/result through an increasingly narrowing canalization of development. Organisms do not *grow into a form* (“target morphology”), but rather develop, *resulting in it* (“resulting morphology”). The difference between these growth modes is easily appreciated in their interaction with the environment: in the first strategy, the outcome is strictly set, while the second one allows intergenerational modifications to occur in accordance with changes taking place in the environment. Development, thus, —even if it includes target-directed cell movements— can be compared to a sort of extremely complex and highly regulated *crystallization*, which does not require any reference with which its advance should be compared (Levin, 2020). Living forms familiar to us, thus, result from the relatively stable environment they develop within (and, in many cases, from which influence they additionally isolate their ontogenesis). Morphological changes induced by changes in the environment (Schmalhausen, 1949; Tung and Levin, 2020) support this view on development, and are one of the sources of phenotypic variation in changing environments: gene(s) responsible for a certain phenotypic trait may still remain the same, but the expression of the trait itself can differ in different environmental conditions (Schmalhausen, 1982). This behavior is countered by an opposite tendency that becomes evident at the populational level: phenotypic traits constituting the so-called wild-type phenotype appear to be more stable than the genetic basis underlying it (Schmalhausen, 1982; Rautian et al., 2008; Shishkin, 2010; Shishkin, 2018). Thus, very similar to the case we presented for cells in the developing organism (section 2.4.), observable living forms arise as “norms of reaction” in environments which typically have a limited and defined range of variability. The fitness of the emerged living form with the available environment determines whether it will survive (“be selected for”) or not (Schmalhausen, 1949, 1982). Interestingly, a similar regulation has been noticed at the tissular level: mechanisms controlling organ size regulate their overall size, but not the underlying proliferation of individual cells (Svetlov, 1978; Eder et al., 2017). Thus, development (and specification, as its particular case) can be considered to peak when no specialization/specification is further possible within the given environment.

These are elements of the general theory of development we will not approach in the present work.

Another important concept in developmental biology is that of *critical phases*. This concept is typically applied to postnatal stages, when specific neural competencies are acquired (for example, development of monocular vision under unilateral visual deprivation, or language acquisition), although a view exists, extending criticality to earlier stages of development (Svetlov, 1978; Teltsov et al., 2008). Before a critical phase, a tissue is undetermined and labile, but as it approaches a critical phase, its development becomes more and more determined until it reaches the maximal determination specific for that phase; in some cases the organism at such stages may have a “mosaic” organization (Svetlov, 1978). During critical phases, the developing organism displays the highest sensitivity toward external factors, among them — the “natural” ones which determine its normal development. Every such phase serves as a determinant of the next phase, and prepares the organism for it (Teltsov et al., 2008), making development a step-wise process rather than a continuous one. In humans, for example, 14 such critical phases were identified, 6 pre-birth and 8 post-birth (Teltsov et al., 2008). Interestingly, as determination increases, the development of specified parts may become asynchronous, and different embryos may display variations in the rates of their parts’ development (as observed in Levin, 2020). This observation is reminiscent of the roles epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition (EMT) and mesenchymal-to-epithelial transition (MET) play at the cellular level during development (Kim et al., 2017) and in cancer, in this last case mesenchymal cells displaying higher independence (=more “determinance”) and less susceptibility to treatments (“factors perturbing development”). On the other hand, changes in the structure of the relationship between developing parts during the “mosaic” phase may be responsible for the emergence of aberrant phenotypes like two-headedness in planarias (Whited and Levin, 2019). Mechanistically, this process can result from the bioelectric- and Ca^{2+} -dependent regionalization and gap junction permeability reduction, described above (Brodskiy et al., 2019 and section 2.4.1.3.)

A brief analysis of the examples presented in section 2.4.1.1.-3. suggests that any of the cell-cell interaction (differentiating/specificating) means, taken alone, is enough to trigger differentiation. Then, why are different differentiation means required during development? In previous sections we analyzed each means separately, however, in tissues they operate jointly and in conditions of cell populational heterogeneity (i.e., in cells belonging to the same population, but displaying variable properties). This suggests that, once regions become determined, it is hard to distinguish the effect of individual means at the cellular level: different cells (belonging to a same population) will respond differently to their action. This is the level of “noise” of molecular mechanisms, possibly underlying what could be called “epithelial-mesenchymal-epithelial transitions” (EMET; see Wang and Unternaehrer, 2018 for a similar concept) as a reflection of the differentiation-driven dynamics of the epithelial-mesenchymal plasticity (EMP; Yang et al., 2020) observable in

tissues. Such EMET waves (with mesenchymal states reportedly being less sensitive to the action of external factors) could be responsible for the emergence of the critical phases of development, mentioned above.

The complex and joint action of means of different natures, thus, ensures correct differentiation/specification within a heterogeneous cell population, and its maintenance in this state. Particular physico-chemical and spatio-temporal properties of means confer the specificity required for this process, making it robust (as proposed for plant morphogenesis; Landrein and Ingram, 2019). *Chemical signals*, for instance, once synthesized, can remain and act over time; they can be compartmentalized, transported or inactivated, forming complex patterns; they can evoke reactions either through changes in sensitivity toward them, or through changes in their production or utilization. These features make signaling through chemical compounds relatively slow. Also, the amount of chemical substance produced may carry information on either the size of the zone producing it, or the zone's physiological activity. On the other hand, *electrical signals* can be quickly modified, but their generation and maintenance require constant energy spending. Unlike chemical signals, electrical ones offer a relatively rapid feedback over long distances. Finally, *mechanical cues* are the quickest-acting, they provide a crowd-dependent feedback, bear topological information, and can add tissular anisotropy information which can otherwise pass unperceived if individual cells are observed (Jiao, 2019). Moreover, the ability of increased cell contractility and low adhesion to the extracellular medium to immediately induce a migratory phenotype (Liu et al., 2015), suggests the possibility that, during development, cell migration takes place along gradually establishing mechanically-defined routes until the appropriate “mechanical niche” is encountered. Thus, the joint action of means allows to unify the response of ensembles of heterogeneous cells and defines their dynamics of growth and development. Examples of such interactions in animals were presented in previous sections. In the plant *Arabidopsis*, the sepal size and the growth pattern of the cells composing it, are apparently slightly affected by the size of individual cells, suggesting the existence of a balance between stresses, cell wall mechanics and cells' sizes (Kierzkowski and Routier-Kierzkowska, 2019).

Changes in the relative importance of different means may also denote transitions through critical phases of development, and more generally — may underlie interspecific phylogenetic differences in the differentiation-to-specification relationship. In *Danio rerio*, for example, it was observed that tailbud elongation and generation of new somites is associated with changes in tissular stiffness and fluidity (Serwane et al., 2016). Changes in the sensitivity toward the action of means also appear to be responsible for the existence of the so-called “competency windows” (Sagner and Briscoe, 2017).

Taking together these concepts, and the role Ca^{2+} signaling plays in cellular-level programs, described before, we can attempt to determine what the general role of Ca^{2+} signaling is in

mediating cell-cell interactions in multicellular organisms, and how Ca^{2+} signaling is interleaved with the action of differentiation/specification means.

First, Ca^{2+} ion possesses a dual “electro-chemical” nature, with specificity conferred by its physico-chemical properties (Carafoli and Krebs, 2016), and sensitivity of its fluxes toward mechanical stimuli conferred by the gating properties of many of its transporters (e.g., TRP channels in animals). Together, these features make from Ca^{2+} and its transients an ideal confluence point of the three cell-cell interaction means, and at the same time — a factor able to modify them, closing the feedback loop. At least, for mechanical and electrical cues, results suggesting the existence of such feedback have been firmly obtained. For example, TRPs mediate the Ca^{2+} influx that remodels the actin cytoskeleton, and the cytoskeleton, in turn, is able to change the channels’ location, their interaction with other proteins, and gating (Canales et al., 2019). A similar bidirectional influence has been shown for the central nervous system: in experiments with artificially-induced morphologies, it plays the role of both the protagonist and the subject of remodeling (Bischof et al., 2019). In some cases the effect of a means is not directly mediated by Ca^{2+} signaling: some mechanical stimuli are able to directly alter genes’ expression (Sun et al., 2020). However, it can be expected that in such cases Ca^{2+} signaling provides the feedback that determines the cell’s further behavior induced by the action of such stimuli.

This feedback structure may be functionally conserved among different organisms, differing only the involved species-specific factors (=compounds). Apparently, only Ca^{2+} signaling remained unchanged across phylae as a common factor and a conserved confluence point of cell-cell interaction means. This proposal suggests that functional analogies between non-related compounds involved in morphogenesis can be identified through the structural analysis of the morphogenetic processes. In other words, the same pattern of “abnormal” evolution observed for the Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit (Marchadier et al., 2016) can probably be distinguished for chemical compounds of different nature if their *functions* are taken into account, *instead of their genetic kinship*. The functional complementarity observed for many morphogens in phylogenetically-distant organisms (Gilbert, 2010) potentially supports this view.

During ontogenesis, embryonic cells differentiate either through autonomous or conditional specification (see Grobstein, 1962; Svetlov, 1978; Gilbert, 2010). It can be expected that the corresponding Ca^{2+} signaling toolkits are established in a similar way: first, following genetically-defined mechanisms in the case of autonomous specification, and in a labile and context-depending way, in the case of conditional specification. Understanding how the calcium signaling toolkit is established during development requires knowing the expression levels and turnover rates of Ca^{2+} -handling proteins induced by different stimuli, the Ca^{2+} signals evoked by those stimuli, and the activation of Ca^{2+} -dependent transcription factors — an enormous work that will be skipped in the present introductory study. We can, nevertheless, propose a general mechanism describing how Ca^{2+} signaling is modified

during development: proliferation and differentiation are apparently activated by a generalized cytosolic Ca^{2+} increase of an irrelevant origin, but then physiological processes restrict the possible origins of the Ca^{2+} fluxes associated with their execution (possibly — as a readout of the differentiation process; see examples in Paudel et al., 2018). And at this or a later stage Ca^{2+} -handling proteins (including Ca^{2+} transporters) become themselves important as interaction partners. As we propose, modulation of these transitions by external conditions (including the modulation of background Ca^{2+} levels, as it occurs during dorso-ventral patterning in *Drosophila*, McMillen et al., 2019) is what determines the conditional character of specification.

As suggested in sections 2.1, 2.3.1, 2.3.5., within regions in conditionally-specified tissues, differentiation and tissue specification modify Ca^{2+} signaling functional blocks. In previous sections we mentioned examples of Ca^{2+} transients observed during early stages of embryogenesis in animals (Paudel et al., 2018; Brodskiy et al., 2019) and at the apical meristem in plants (Li et al., 2019): spikes (confined to individual cells) and waves (propagating to several contiguous cells). In animals, both these types of transient are observed during gastrulation, and display an increased frequency at the late stages of neural tube closure (Paudel et al., 2018). We mentioned some processes that accompany this activity, and that are affected by Ca^{2+} signaling disruption: mitoses, apical contraction, cell polarization, migration, width of Sox2 expression zones, and regionalization (see section 2.4.1.3.). We propose that, within regions, Ca^{2+} transients synchronize these relatively autonomous cellular-level processes, and presented examples of their regulation by Ca^{2+} in previous sections. Thus, Ca^{2+} transients not only promote these processes (permissive role), but also serve as a readout of their outcome (instructive role; Brodskiy et al., 2019). In this way, Ca^{2+} signaling exerts its orchestrating function (Fig 5). In plants, long distance signaling (and Ca^{2+} signaling as its particular case) is proposed to coordinate the organized growth of the different plant's parts (Carmen, 2008), which in these organisms display higher autonomy than in animals.

Different types of tissues are induced with different probability. In experiments with boiled organizers or with starving planarians, it was determined that the nervous system is induced with the highest probability and displays the highest resistance to starvation-induced degeneration in the following sequence (from the lowest resistance to the highest one): reproductive > muscle > glands > epithelia > neural (Svetlov, 1978). From the evolutionary point of view, this could have resulted from the important role the nervous system started playing in morphological coordination (Fields et al., 2020).

Ca^{2+} signaling is considered to be an essential factor regulating neural differentiation. Acknowledging this role, the concept of calcium activity-mediated neurotransmitter specification was proposed, which establishes a correlation between the free Ca^{2+} availability and the proportion of excitatory and inhibitory neuron types, a parameter that can predict the onset of autism spectrum disorders, and of the Rett and fragile X syndroms

(Paudel et al., 2018). Reflecting the importance of the origin of the Ca^{2+} flux for tissue specification, it was observed that neurogenesis relies on VGCCs, while myogenesis is driven by SOCE (Paudel et al., 2018). Interestingly, vascular injury induces a phenotype switch of smooth muscle cells from a quiescent and contractile phenotype, which relies on VGCCs for Ca^{2+} entry, to a proliferating one, which depends on SOCE for Ca^{2+} influx (Stewart et al., 2014).

The results presented above suggest that differentiation starts simultaneously in several directions, or, more specifically, as it was noted before — specification is gradual, and proceeds from a more generalized state toward several specialized ones. This gradual specification is accompanied by a restructuring of the Ca^{2+} signaling functional blocks, allowing cells to perform their function at each stage of ontogenesis. Thus, *differentiation should not be considered a (single) program within the proliferation-quiescence functional block, but rather a transition process to a spectrum of possible end fate programs*, that very probably can give origin to specific minor functional blocks (e.g., “fertilization”, “synaptic transmission”, “establishment of symbiosis with N_2 -fixing bacteria”, and others). Differentiation signaling pathways and transcription factors are in most cases conserved between tissues and states of competency (Sagner and Briscoe, 2017), and thus, it would be interesting to analyze how they relate to changes in the Ca^{2+} signaling functional blocks, and whether common steps exist in the transitions to the differentiated states (potentially allowing to determine “degrees of differentiation freedom” for a particular tissue).

In plants, the requirement of Ca^{2+} increase for cell proliferation apparently contradicts this ion’s role in cell cycle arrest induced by abiotic stresses (e.g., Sano et al., 2006). We have previously proposed that this abrupt reaction can constitute an adaptive mechanism that plants developed as a response to external cues (Pérez Koldenkova and Hatsugai, 2018), possibly forming part of the general life strategy of plants to activate dedifferentiation mechanisms in response to the effect of different stressors (Grafi et al., 2011; Sugiyama, 2015). Thus, plants achieve a degree of differentiation which is associated with physiological adaptations to a certain environment. However, upon a sudden change to these conditions, plants abruptly stop their growth processes, and then —through a mechanism of partial dedifferentiation (resembling animal EMT?)— start adapting to the new conditions. The permanent need to adapt to the changing environment is probably one of the reasons why plant cells do not attain high degrees of differentiation as it occurs in animals (Matos et al., 2014), and another explanation for the remarkable proteomic redundancy observable in the former.

Of note, particular gating properties of different Ca^{2+} transporters may confer specific “functional” traits to functional blocks. For example, the intrinsically oscillatory Ca^{2+} -releasing activity of IP_3 Rs homologs might be responsible for an entire spectrum of repetitive phenomena, like the contractile vacuole functioning in *Paramecium tetraurelia*, and flagella undulation in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* (Wheeler and Brownlee, 2008).

It should be mentioned that in many —if not all— cases cell-cell interaction means involve not only Ca^{2+} signaling but also other signaling pathways: ROS, NO, pH, and their corresponding cascades, which may diversify both the dynamics of development, and the resulting form, making its attainment process robust. As an example, in a previous work we proposed that the responsive phenotype of plant tendrils may result from a particular proportion of ROS and Ca^{2+} signaling (Pérez Koldenkova and Hatsugai, 2018).

Another visible phenomenon that can result from cell-cell interaction in the specific case of animals is collective cell migration. This migration type is observed in certain cancers, during neural crest development and wound healing, and in aggregates of *Dictyostelium* (Artemenko et al., 2014; Yang et al., 2020). The specific mechanisms of collective migration execution can differ across species, but at least during development they seem to be chemotaxis-driven (Fujimori et al., 2019; Shellard and Mayor, 2019). Collective migration is characterized by the presence of two cell types, leaders and followers. Leader cells resemble mesenchymal cells, and migrate through the retrograde F actin flow mechanism, while followers are characterized by tight intercellular contacts (Fujimori et al., 2019; Krakhmal et al., 2015). Leader cells do not reach a fully mesenchymal state, but instead rearrange their junctions' dynamics to exhibit collective movement; moreover, in some cases (like during chicken epiblast morphogenesis) EMT is not involved in this phenomenon (Yang et al., 2020). Nevertheless, similar to cells that have undergone mesenchymal migration, tumor cells engaged in collective migration display higher resistance to chemo- and radio-therapy (Krakhmal et al., 2015), suggesting that both phenomena may be based on similar principles.

Collective migration has also been subdivided: collective migration itself (as the organized and joint migration of independent cells), and supracellular migration, when migrating cells behave as a single cluster of a larger size (Shellard and Mayor, 2019). These two subtypes differ, for example, in their polarization response and the force generated by the sensed stimuli — either at the level of individual cells (collective migration), or at the level of the entire group (supracellular migration; Shellard and Mayor, 2019). Interestingly, in supracellular clusters, individual cells show “atomistic” properties: they engage in a “retrograde cell flow” similar to the flow of actin in individual cells, and the cell-level actin polarization corresponds to that of the cell position (front or rear) within the supracellular cluster (Shellard and Mayor, 2019). Synchronization across the whole entity involves contact inhibition of locomotion (CIL), whereby cell collision induces repolarization and changes the direction of their migration, however the exact mechanism is currently unknown. It is possible that Ca^{2+} waves similar to those observed during *Dictyostelium* aggregation can be responsible for synchronizations.

2.4.3. Cancer

Intracellular Ca^{2+} concentrations in tumor cells is several folds higher than in normal cells, and the exact source of this Ca^{2+} does not appear to be important for their proliferation.

Cancer cells can achieve high cytosolic Ca^{2+} levels through downregulation or reduced expression of Ca^{2+} -extruding pumps, or by enhanced expression of Ca^{2+} influx channels (Humeau et al., 2017).

Despite the overall promiscuity of cancer cells in regard to the origin of their cytosolic Ca^{2+} level, particular cancer types may display association to changes in the expression of specific Ca^{2+} -handling proteins (Humeau et al., 2017). Such associations have been thoroughly documented, and their roles in the malignant phenotype appearance have been explained (Prevarskaya et al., 2013; Hoth et al., 2016; Humeau et al., 2017; Roberts-Thomson et al., 2019). Nevertheless, little is known on why do certain cancer types prefer specific mechanisms to maintain their Ca^{2+} homeostasis. It has been shown that even acquisition of resistance to some therapies can be linked to specific Ca^{2+} -permeable ion channels (Roberts-Thomson et al., 2019).

Mutations in the Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit are not considered cancer-drivers *per se*, however, upon appearance of the minimal cancer-driver mutations, Ca^{2+} signaling can start influencing the kinetics of cancer progression and metastasis (Hoth, 2016), deviating its development from the organism's one, and contributing to the appearance of cancer hallmarks (uncontrolled proliferation, metastasis, invasion ability) and further cancer development (Déliot and Constantin, 2015; Humeau et al., 2017). For example, STIM/Orai or TRPV5/6 do not belong to cancer-driver genes, but their overexpression strongly contributes to the acceleration of cell proliferation and cancer phenotype acquisition (Hoth, 2016). Similarly, human gliomas, breast, ovarian, prostate, colon and esophageal cancers express alternative splice variants of T-type VGCCs (Cui et al., 2017), while breast cancer can express higher levels of either TRPM7 or TRPM8 which serve as markers of different prognosis, allowing both of these changes to preserve cancer cells' malignancy phenotype (Cui et al., 2017). Differences in the expression of TRPM7/TRPM8 in breast cancers are also linked to the role estrogen, as a long-distance chemical differentiating means, can play in the development of these cancer types: TRPM8-overexpressing cells are still sensitive to estrogen-induced differentiation (this property is used with therapeutic goals, to direct the development of this cancer type), while TRPM7 is overexpressed in a more aggressive, estrogen-insensitive breast cancer type, and promotes its metastasis (Cui et al., 2017; Paupe and Prudent, 2018).

Malignant transformation can be accompanied not only by changes in the expression of Ca^{2+} handling proteins, but also by their "rewiring", remodelling of Ca^{2+} storing organelles, and the ultimate establishment of suitable microenvironmental conditions ("the niche") for cancer to progress. For example, oncogenes Bcl-XL and Mcl-1 sensitize IP_3 Rs to lower levels of IP_3 , promoting Ca^{2+} leak from the ER (Bittremieux et al., 2016), at the same time inhibiting mitochondrial Ca^{2+} uptake through VDAC1 at the mitochondria-associated ER membranes, MAMs, (Kerkhofs et al., 2017), thus allowing cells to escape Ca^{2+} overload-mediated apoptosis. ER Ca^{2+} levels are also reduced by SERCA inhibition or its lowered

expression by the action of Bcl-2 or RAS oncogenes (Bittremieux et al., 2016). Human breast cancer tumours express higher levels of the Golgi network secretory pathway $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Mn}^{2+}$ -ATPase 2 (SPCA2), however in cancer cells this protein does not reduce the cytosolic Ca^{2+} levels, as it starts pairing with the plasma membrane ORAI1 channel, forming a novel constitutively active Ca^{2+} influx channel (Prevarskaya et al., 2013). Malignant transformation is accompanied by lysosome volume increase and their repositioning to the cell periphery (Faris et al., 2019), and mitochondria fragmentation, favoring cell migration (Paupe and Prudent, 2018), as it was described in section 2.2. The Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit is also involved in the creation of the tumor microenvironment: SOCE apparently participates in the generation of cancer-induced inflammation and necrosis in a model of T-cell acute lymphoblastic leukemia, while TRPV4 is linked to angiogenesis (although it is not clear whether the inhibition or the activation of this channel is important for this process; Roberts-Thomson et al., 2019).

A switch between programs (“proliferation”, “quiescence”, “migration”, etc.) upon the substitution of the Ca^{2+} source has also been documented (Humeau et al., 2017). This suggests that functional blocks in cancer cells are modified. For instance, melanoma cells can rely on NAADP-induced Ca^{2+} release from endolysosomes to sustain their proliferation and migration (Faris et al., 2019). Particular transporters can both favor or inhibit the manifestation of the Ca^{2+} -dependent programs, in other words — the operation or the functional outcome of a particular block. For example, overexpression of ORAI channels can lead either to increased proliferation (a pro-oncogenic effect) or apoptosis (an anti-oncogenic effect) (Hoth, 2016). Such duality in the potential outcome makes it difficult to obtain a desired therapeutic effect by addressing a single Ca^{2+} -handling protein.

Expression of the embryonic stem cells-associated transcription factors *nanog*, *oct4*, *sox2*, and *c-myc* (Moore and Lyle, 2011) favors EMT and low differentiation degrees characteristic for cancer stem cells, and presumably allows them to adapt and survive in the new (including therapy-induced) conditions emerging in the organism. The loss or alteration of Ca^{2+} -dependent cell cycle regulators through which the organism can control morphogenesis, like those belonging to the cyclin D/CDK4/pRb/E2F pathway, which is affected in more than 80% of cancers (Kahl and Means, 2003; Moore and Lyle, 2011), contributes to the expansion of the possible evolutionary strategies that become available to cancer cells within the organism. In this way, the fitness, or “supercompetitor” capacity of cancerous cells results from the bypass of the “normal” intra-organismal developmental constraints, and from development following the tumor’s own (*also evolving*) differentiating rules. Using a currently relevant analogy, it can be said that cancer —as a system capable to increase its own complexity— displays the same sort of “intelligence” which in some works is claimed for plants.

Importantly, in cancer studies, EMT is primarily associated with *dedifferentiation* (Wang and Unternaehrer, 2018), although the ability to produce metastases requires cells to

preserve, at least partially, the plasticity to revert to the epithelial state (Ye and Weinberg, 2015; Zhang and Weinberg, 2018; Yang et al., 2020). In this regard, it is interesting to mention that even aggressive cancer forms can be normalized in embryonic environments (Levin, 2020), probably due to similarities between such dedifferentiating environments and those established within healing wounds (Wong and Whited, 2020). Thus, although EMT is only a step within the dedifferentiation-toward-a-new-differentiation process (Wang and Unternaehrer, 2018, or EMET, as we have coined it in section 2.4.2.), it is possible that in cancer the mechanisms of “definitive” differentiation are affected, thus securing the observed metastable epithelial-mesenchymal plasticity. Observations that activation and execution of EMT programs not necessarily require introduction of changes into the DNA sequence, and in some cases can occur at the post-translational level (Yang et al., 2020) may support this view.

Interestingly, the endolysosomal compartment seems to play an important role in malignancy emergence in cancer. First, several cancer types (pancreatic carcinoma, prostate cancer, metastatic breast and lung cancers) display resistance to anoikis — an apoptosis program that in normal cells is activated when integrin-dependent adherence to the extracellular matrix is lost (Kim et al., 2017), and integrin transport in animal cells is mediated by acidic Ca^{2+} stores (see section 2.2.2.1.). These compartments are also involved in the appearance of highly migratory phenotypes and drug resistance (apparently — through a pH-dependent trapping mechanism). But more importantly, the endolysosomal compartment apparently participates in the emergence of stemness traits in cancer cells (Salerno et al., 2014; Kim et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2020). As we could notice from the examples presented in section 2.2., lysosomal Ca^{2+} -permeable ion channels are important key factors conferring malignancy features to transformed cells, which, on the other hand, may correspond to an exacerbated activity of functions typically present in the course of normal differentiation.

Cancer, overall, is an example of deregulated development, in which the effects of non-coordinated cell-cell interaction means can still be traced. For example, increased sympathetic and decreased parasympathetic nerve density in tumors are associated with poor clinical outcome (Kamiya et al., 2019), and changes in bioelectrical potential seemingly possess the ability to induce EMT (McMillen et al., 2019). On the other hand, abnormal mechanical environment may alter normal organogenesis and produce malformations (Mammoto and Ingber, 2010). Examples of tumor development by chemical cues were presented in previous sections.

Taking together the data presented above, the proposal to revert cancer by targeting defective Ca^{2+} signaling (Prevarskaya et al., 2013; Cui et al., 2017; Roberts-Thomson et al., 2019) looks much like an attempt to revert an evolving system to its original state. Targeting Ca^{2+} signaling can undoubtedly allow to modify cancer cell programs, although the extent to which these programs can be “normalized” depends not only on how much

have the original programs been affected, but also on the degree of alteration of the tissue-specifying means within the cancer niche which supports the transformed tissue development. The normalization of the niche, however, can be attempted by the external modification of its bioelectrical field using so-called electroceuticals (Cervera et al., 2019; Emmons-Bell et al., 2019). On the other hand, such manipulations can also lead to further evolution of cancer forms. In any case, cancer probably offers the strongest evidence of the importance Ca^{2+} signaling has in orchestrating development in the course of evolution of living organisms.

2.4.4. Regeneration

Empirically, two non-mutually exclusive types of regeneration can be distinguished: epimorphosis and morphallaxis. Differences between these two regeneration modes (and in some cases — their overall applicability to the description of the regeneration process) are currently under discussion. In our work we will follow the definitions proposed by J. Pelletieri (2019): *epimorphosis* — is “a regenerative process in which proliferation of stem/progenitor cells leads to the development of a new part”, whereas *reorganization or morphallaxis* — is a “process in which anatomical patterning, scale, and proportion are restored through remodeling of an existing part”.

Why is there regeneration at all? It is very probably that in animals this property appeared together with development: in more primitive animals, similar to plants — to compensate for hampered functional capacity, while later in evolution — to recover (through the action of cell-cell interaction means) the form through which the organism’s functional capacity is attained. Emergence of form, thus, appears to be tightly linked to the closure of a “field” created by the three cell-cell interaction means, with regeneration aimed at recovering this field’s integrity, if broken. We should note that the “combined” regenerative field, induced by the three analyzed means, cannot *per se* be directly visualized, and an insight on its action can only be obtained through the analysis of individual means, as has been expressed in regard to plant organogenesis (Besnard et al., 2011). Thus, in epimorphosis, the field should activate specification of dormant undifferentiated tissue progenitors, while in the case of morphallaxis, the field should induce cells dedifferentiation with their posterior re-differentiation. This is in agreement with observations that in flatworms and cnidarians, which display epimorphy, regeneration depends on two neoblasts subpopulations characterized by different differentiation degrees (Marchant, 2019; Amiel et al., 2019), and by the fact that the axolotl (*Ambystoma mexicanum*), a highly-regenerating vertebrate, is characterized by neoteny (juvenilization). For comparison, in chicks and rats, regeneration of a damaged differentiated nerve requires the elaboration of new growth cones transiently expressing Kv3.4 potassium channels that locally lower its excitability and promotes its outgrowth (Whited and Levin, 2019). This result suggests a way in which function is temporarily “turned off” to enable regeneration.

The regeneration ability, as well as the body part that can be regenerated, may differ at different stages of development, even in highly-regenerating species. This feature results from the staggered dynamics in which development progresses, characterized by the presence of critical phases of relatively autonomous development of the organism parts (see section 2.4.2.; Svetlov, 1978). Thus, it is probable that the body part that can be regenerated depends on the zones' limits that are established during development, or on the limits to which dedifferentiation can expand, depending on the regeneration type.

Currently there is a lack of criteria to compare regeneration processes across divergent groups of animals in regard to mechanisms, the involved cell types or the molecular mediators (Sinigaglia and Averof, 2019), possibly due to the reasons mentioned above and different proportions of the means involved in the execution of regeneration (see below). More generally, regeneration highlights the differences existing in the whole-to-part relationship between animals and plants: in animals, regeneration aims at recovering a relatively fixed shape, while in plants (and some coelenterates) "regeneration" (Ikeuchi et al., 2016) reflects rather a process of recovering functional capacities (compensatory regeneration; Svetlov, 1978), without strict attachment to some rigid form.

Mechanistically, in planarians, regeneration activates position-control genes as a first response. Morphogens participate in the definition of body polarity: Wnt regulates the antero-posterior axis establishment, while BMP is responsible for the dorso-ventral axis, and both of these pathways depend on Ca^{2+} signaling (Marchant, 2019). Interestingly, the regeneration ability seems to be linked to muscle contraction, at least in some invertebrates (Marchant, 2019). Apart from the suspected presence of position-control genes in muscles (Marchant, 2019), it is possible that contraction itself may act as an additional cue inducing cell elongation and migration, finally ending in regeneration (see Paudel et al., 2018). Of note, the proportion of the three means in regeneration can apparently vary between organisms. For example, sea stars' regeneration entirely depends on the nervous system activity, and is arrested if regenerating arms are denervated (Sinigaglia and Averof, 2019).

For the nervous system, several forms of action during regeneration have been proposed (Sinigaglia and Averof, 2019): all-or-none, permissive or instructive, and exerted either in a direct or indirect form. Moreover, in different organisms structures responsible for signaling can differ: in some cases, nerves are proposed to act as a source of local signals, in other cases this role is undertaken by nerve-associated cells, while in a third case nerves can serve as a source of systemic signals. In different organisms, the nervous system has been shown to promote cell proliferation, although less is known about its effect on differentiation (probably, as a result of a different contribution of individual means to development and regeneration, as mentioned above).

Other details of regeneration regulation by cell-cell interaction means are presented in works by Wong and Whited (2020; in comparison with tumorigenesis) and Svetlov (1978;

of particular interest are cited examples on the effect of regeneration inductors of similar nature, but originating from different body parts), and others.

Evidence of the importance of Ca^{2+} for successful regeneration in animals is vast: similar to development, regeneration does not proceed in absence of Ca^{2+} , polarity is affected if Ca^{2+} homeostasis is perturbed at the same time, or shortly after wounding; in regenerating planarias, injury-induced neoblasts proliferation is accompanied by changes in cytosolic Ca^{2+} level that correlates with changes in neurotransmitter content (as it occurs during development, section 2.4.2.); in addition, Ca^{2+} -regulated signaling pathways involved in development (Wnt, BMP, Hh) also participate in patterning and specification during regeneration in planaria (Marchant, 2019). Generally speaking, Ca^{2+} influx is part of the early response to wounding, however, how the regeneration response is regulated by this signaling pathway is not entirely understood (Marchant, 2019). Apparently, part of the Ca^{2+} -dependent response is induced by cell layers or muscle contractions which expel potentially damaged cells, although the contraction itself may serve as a mechanical cue promoting regeneration (Paudel et al., 2018; Marchant, 2019). Importantly, blocking Ca^{2+} signaling impairs wound healing (Paudel et al., 2018), possibly by preventing proliferation-promoting, EMT-inducing cytosolic Ca^{2+} increase, potentially supporting our conjecture about cytosolic Ca^{2+} level differences between cells engaged either in proliferation or differentiation (section 2.3.5.).

Similar to development, regeneration is linked to Ca^{2+} influx mediated by VGCCs or TRPs, and amplified by IP_3 Rs and RYRs (Marchant, 2019). Hints on the particular roles of different channels in *Dugesia japonica* regeneration were obtained in experiments with CaCl_2 replacement by BaCl_2 in the media (Emmons-Bell et al., 2019). Exposure of the regenerating planaria to BaCl_2 resulted in acute toxicity and degeneration, however, after that, worms regenerated heads adapted to BaCl_2 -containing medium. Interestingly, if Ca^{2+} and Cl^- channels were blocked, no initial excitotoxicity was observed in response to BaCl_2 exposure, while deactivation of TRPMs prevented adaptation (Emmons-Bell et al., 2019). Other molecular mechanisms involved in wound closure are detailed by Paudel et al., (2018) and Marchant (2019). Of note, *Caenorhabditis elegans*, the cells of which differentiate in an autonomous way during development (see section 2.3.5.), do not express, unlike planarians, voltage-gated Na^+ channels, hyperpolarization activated CNGCs, or TPCs (Marchant, 2019), suggesting that these transporters may be specifically required for regeneration.

What are the factors that signal about a successfully-completed regeneration process? Can regeneration be induced “to continue” once the wound is closed? If we suppose that the development peaks when no specialization/specification is further possible within the given environment (as proposed in section 2.4.2.), it can be suggested that regeneration (at least in animals) follows similar rules. Regeneration, thus, emerges as a process of closure of the field produced by the three cell-cell interaction means, and even if the associated Ca^{2+}

signaling is artificially kept active, it will rather produce malformations. This view resembles the Harold Dvorak's view of tumors as wounds that do not heal, and highlights the similarity between tumor formation and epimorphic regeneration (Wong and Whited, 2020). Interestingly, healing and development look different in this case: a wound on the *Drosophila* pupal notum induces actin polarization in several layers at the wound border, and its assembling into a supracellular cable, apparently aiding collective migration to close the injury, whereas for dorsal closure during the normal course of development this cable is dispensable (Shellard and Mayor, 2019). Importantly, regeneration apparently aims at recovering the integrity of the shape field that arises during the sequence of critical phases (section 2.4.2.) and according to the specification zones established during this process. This could be the reason why regeneration recovers the integrity even of aberrant phenotypes such as that of the two-headed planarians (Whited and Levin, 2019).

As mentioned at the beginning of this section, plant regeneration modes —*de novo* organogenesis, and somatic *in vitro* embryogenesis (Ikeuchi et al., 2016)— are processes greatly differing from regeneration in animals, and wound closure, if present, does not aim at recovering some specific form, but rather a functional capacity (compensatory regeneration, Svetlov, 1978). Still, an interesting characteristic of plants is the robustness of their shoot apical meristem (SAM) against treatments that aim to change its shape by modifying the proliferation rate (Besnard et al., 2011), a property that is observed in the root meristem as well. SAM resilience to shape change has been proposed to emerge from the mutual regulation between mechanical forces and auxin transport: mechanical forces induce Ca^{2+} transients that influence auxin transporters polarity distribution, while auxin signaling reduces the apoplastic pH, activating cellulose-modifying enzymes, favoring in this way the change of mechanical properties of the meristem (Besnard et al., 2011; Landrein and Ingram, 2019; Li et al., 2019). Another factor that presumably maintains the SAM's form is the dynamic and restricted communication between cells from different subdomains of the meristem (the size exclusion limit, Besnard et al., 2011), which depends on Ca^{2+} -regulated contraction of plasmodesmata — structures, that play in plants a role similar to that of tight junctions in animals. Interestingly, the origin of spontaneous Ca^{2+} spikes and oscillations is currently unknown, but they have been proposed to reflect changes in the mechanical interactions between expanding cells, as their period (20-60 mins) is similar to that of *Arabidopsis thaliana* micronutations (Li et al., 2019).

3. The “triggering” role of Ca^{2+} signals

By the *triggering* role of Ca^{2+} signaling we understand the direct, “classic”, participation of Ca^{2+} as a messenger in the activation or inhibition of physiological processes. We stand in front of the triggering role when a stimulus is at the cellular level transduced into a Ca^{2+} signal which produces a response. A typical example of this role is the participation of Ca^{2+} in the excitation-contraction coupling in muscle cells. This “traditional” role of Ca^{2+}

signaling is thoroughly dissected elsewhere (White, 2003; Clapham, 2007; Dodd et al., 2010; Bootman, 2012; Vanneste and Friml, 2013; Himschoot et al., 2015) and thus, its analysis will be omitted in the present work.

Nevertheless, an important issue arises in relation to this role, namely — the responsive remodeling of the Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit as a function of its workload. Phenomena like — again related to muscle— atrophy, under conditions of reduced exercise, are well known, suggesting the involvement in this case of adaptive mechanisms capable to dynamically modify the Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit, in accordance with the organism requirements. Such feedback suggests the existence of a coupling between the two roles of Ca^{2+} signaling, which is briefly analyzed below.

4. Orchestrating-to-triggering role transition and orchestrating-triggering coupling

As soon as the developing organism is exposed to external cues, its further development (and the associated differentiation) continues in a manner intrinsically bound to the spectra of types and intensities of stimuli that become available to it. In this regard, it can be recalled that animals evolved towards the stabilization of conditions of development, while plants are exposed to such conditions almost from the beginning of their development (although such exposure can at least partially be compensated by transgenerational adaptive mechanisms, see Baker et al., 2019; Dong et al., 2019).

Thus, two following changes of Ca^{2+} signaling can be proposed to take place concomitantly during the course of development:

1) *Orchestrating-to-triggering role transition*. This process, basically, corresponds to the tissular-level Ca^{2+} signaling analog of mesenchymal-to-epithelial transition (MET) and takes place when the cell transits to its terminally-differentiated state and its genetically-established Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit (with or without modifications) starts carrying the “end” functions. During this transition, the elements composing a functional block can be replaced (=experience succession) or be rewired. Nevertheless, under most circumstances preservation of some degree of flexibility/plasticity has to be expected, that can allow the system to “reorchestrate” itself, in accordance with its “usage”/work load, or in response to injuries (like the switching from VGCC-mediated Ca^{2+} entry, typical of contractile cells, to SOCE, as the main Ca^{2+} source in proliferating cells; Stewart et al., 2014).

Other examples of changes accompanying the orchestrating-to-triggering role transition are L-type ($\text{Ca}_v1.2$) Ca^{2+} channels, that mediate spontaneous calcium transients: they are important for axonal growth in developing neurons (Tang et al., 2003), but are less expressed later in life. Similar observations come from studies on cancer development: we mentioned the relocalization of InsP_3Rs and STIM1 from ER-PM junctions induced by cell detachment from the tumor (Okeke et al., 2016); also, the “uncommon” Orai3 isoform, along with the “common” Orai1 , participates in SOCE in estrogen receptor-positive breast

cancer cells (Roberts-Thomson et al., 2019 and references therein). These last examples may point to processes taking place during normal development, as well as accompanying abnormal and malignant development (as a result of incorrect targeting or pairing of Ca^{2+} signaling mechanisms, failures in the activation of the correct triggering role, etc., see Stewart et al., 2014). Orchestrating-to-triggering transition could also explain benign neonate motor phenomena in newborns (Huntsman et al., 2008), as a reflection of the central neural system adaptation and fine tuning to the different inputs from the body itself and the surrounding environment.

2) Linked to the above process is the *orchestrating-triggering coupling* which establishes the feedback necessary to “reconfigure” the available working Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit (i.e., to activate programs of *dedifferentiation* (as part of epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition), further development, degeneration, or senescence) in accordance with the workload and the physiological context. In this regard, it would be interesting to analyze the possibility that the emergence of certain cancer types could be promoted by reduced tissular function, which should otherwise prevent dedifferentiation. Such lack-of-function-dependent transformation could be expected in tissues that are functionally-active only during certain periods of time (e.g., breast, reproductive system, and others).

The degree of interdependence of the above processes may vary between organisms and particular tissues. For example, the visual system in humans is established in a manner almost independent from light levels available to a newborn, while the correct formation and frequency response of the auditory system requires its exposure to appropriate wavelengths stimulation during gestation (Graven and Browne, 2008). Functional stimuli are also known to be required for kidney development in zebrafish and lung maturation in rats (Mammoto and Ingber, 2010). In the case of plants, we proposed previously that propagating long distance signals could play the role of modulators of development, which activate mechanisms of adaptation to sudden changes in an environment a plant is “accustomed” to (Pérez Koldenkova and Hatsugai, 2018).

Cells constitute the minimal essential units of living organisms, and thus the above tissular-level processes have to be realized through the cellular-level Ca^{2+} toolkit. An overview of the mechanisms through which the orchestrating-to-triggering role transition and the orchestrating-triggering coupling can take place in living organisms was provided in previous sections. Their particular details, according to the analysis of the Ca^{2+} signaling proteome evolution, performed by Marchadier and coworkers (2016), should be species- (and tissue-) specific, requiring a separate, case by case, study.

5. Ca^{2+} signaling flexibility and robustness

We presented evidence of the existence of interacting *layers* of Ca^{2+} signaling regulation: *intracellular* Ca^{2+} signaling influences *tissular* differentiation in multicellular organisms,

and *tissular* organization in turn influences the establishment of the *intracellular* Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit of cells as the organism's constituting elements.

Given the depth at which Ca^{2+} signaling is involved in the regulation of developmental processes of different levels, its alterations are reflected in the organism phenotype, and more generally — in the resulting type of living form. In this regard, it is important to highlight two features that characterize how susceptible development is to changes in the Ca^{2+} signaling organization. These proposed features are: 1) Ca^{2+} signaling flexibility, reflecting the plasticity of normal Ca^{2+} signaling, and the extent to which abnormal Ca^{2+} signaling can be compensated, and 2) Ca^{2+} signaling robustness, reflecting how stable Ca^{2+} signaling remains under changing external conditions. These parameters, thus, characterize not only the features of the Ca^{2+} signaling machinery, but also properties of the Ca^{2+} transients themselves.

At the subcellular level, both flexibility and robustness can be relatively easy to isolate, although at the organismal level we should probably refer to a combined feature — the ability of an organism to modify or compensate alterations to its Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit composition/organization (*=flexibility*) in such a way, that it stays viable and able to leave progeny (*=robustness*). Robustness in this case does not necessarily have to arise from the sensitivity reduction of the developing system towards altering factors. It was shown to result as well from “learning”, which restricts the possible “number of ways in which such [factors] can be combined to generate phenotypic outputs” (Brun-Usan and Watson, 2019).

In animals, robustness varies at different stages of development (Svetlov, 1978, see also section 2.4.2), however a smooth transition through such sensitive periods is achieved by increasing the independence of development from (external) environmental factors. Contrary to this, under variable external conditions in which plants have to develop, robustness has to be an intrinsic property of Ca^{2+} signaling, thus demanding more flexibility from the corresponding toolkit. These general requirements fit well with the observed differences in the evolution of the Ca^{2+} signaling proteome in plants and metazoans — in the former, major functional Ca^{2+} signaling groups evolved together, while in the later (presumably — due to relatively constant internal conditions) the mechanisms of Ca^{2+} signaling decoding and relay underwent major expansion (Marchadier et al., 2016).

Defective Ca^{2+} signaling is hard to compensate (Carafoli and Krebs, 2016), and this is apparently achieved only through evolution of populations and the survival of cells/organisms bearing such compensation mechanisms. Some examples can be mentioned: MICU1 (Mitochondrial calcium uniporter1)-KO mice in the C57BL/6N background display high perinatal mortality, although those which survive display symptom alleviation with time (Paupe and Prudent, 2018). In cancer, altered Ca^{2+} signaling can still sustain cellular-level processes, although these are not coordinated with the whole organism development. This is especially noticeable in cases when Ca^{2+} signaling starts

originating, as a result of therapies, from alternatively spliced Ca^{2+} channel variants (Hoth, 2016), or is downregulated to prevent apoptosis, like in the case of Bcl-2 overexpressing cells (Bittremieux et al., 2016), making the reversal of altered Ca^{2+} signaling to the native state a hard-to-attain therapeutic goal. Nevertheless, in some cases defects at the molecular level can still be compensated at the cellular one; for example, *Xenopus laevis* embryos with perturbed Notch signaling were shown to display a normal neuronal gene expression by the swimming tadpole stage — a response that was mediated by modulation of cellular proliferation and apoptosis (Solini et al., 2020).

Ca^{2+} signals' properties themselves differ amongst lineages: amplitude-encoded oscillations, typical for plants, are more robust — resistant to information loss due to environmental (temperature) changes, while frequency encoding, more common in mammals, offers advantages in terms of decoding selectivity, although at the cost of a higher sensitivity to temperature variation (Aguilera et al., 2019).

Conclusions

In cell biology and signaling research, Ca^{2+} is currently viewed as a simple, although versatile, transducer of stimuli. Genes are considered to be the factors responsible for the phenotype, whereas Ca^{2+} is mostly seen as a mere signaling agent functioning within the “built-on-genes” phenotype.

In our work we propose that the role of the Ca^{2+} signaling pathway is wider, and consists not only of stimuli transduction, but also of the establishment of the system itself, in a *responsive* way. Why could, during evolution, arise the necessity of such a particular signaling mechanism, additional to genetic encoding and epigenetic modulation of gene expression by external factors? We propose that Ca^{2+} signaling, apart from unifying inputs from signaling pathways and processes, provides the flexibility and responsiveness required to tune the development to particular surrounding environments, and mediates form adaptation to performed functions. Moreover, while triggering long-lasting responses, Ca^{2+} itself can be rapidly removed from interaction sites. Such similarity of functions attained by Ca^{2+} signaling in different kingdoms looks surprising, considering that animals and plants reached multicellularity independently (Grosberg and Strathmann, 2007; Niklas, 2014). Hence, Ca^{2+} signaling pathway variations across organisms appear to be an extremely rare (if not unique) case of “structural pathway plasticity” in different phylogenetic groups — with a nevertheless-strong attachment to functions— that apparently could not, unlike other components, get convergently replaced during the evolution of multicellular organisms. Such high degree of functional conservancy potentially makes from Ca^{2+} signaling an analog of the Rosetta stone in comparative physiological studies, from which the physiological organization of different organisms can be inferred.

In cells, Ca²⁺ signaling-associated phenomena appear as hard to isolate either at the “phenotypic”/visible level, or at the level of the involved individual molecular players: apparently independent macrophenomena (e.g., “migration”, “proliferation”, “differentiation”, “development”, etc.) are mutually linked through a set of shared molecular effectors. This situation suggests that such phenomena can be approached by analyzing the functional blocks that underlie them. Programs within such blocks can overlap with particular organelles (as it occurs in the case of migration-chemotaxis block and acidic Ca²⁺ stores in animal cells), although this is not strictly required, as evidenced by the more “decentralized” proliferation-quiescence functional block (see a similar conclusion in Marchadier et al., 2016). Analogs of the functional blocks presented here were specifically identified in plants and fungi, and denominated Dynamical Patterning Modules (DPMs). Functionally equivalent DPMs were shown to recruit different structures and materials in different organisms, and to be subjected to natural selection *integrally* (as part of the “phenotype”), and not on the basis of their individual constituting elements (Benítez et al., 2018). An analogous concept of Universal Functional Blocks was also proposed in the work of Alexandr M. Ugolev (1926-1991) (Ugolev, 1991). More generally, the changes in the way how functional blocks interact among themselves can emerge as aromorphoses. Such changes (=aromorphoses) can expand the possible functional patterns that become available to organ systems or the organism itself, as it is shown in the work of Nikolai N. Iordansky (Severtsov, 2010). Altogether, we can appreciate examples of block composition at different suborganismal levels: subcellular (cells displaying variable sets of expressed genes), cellular (cell populational heterogeneity within regions), tissular (with interembryonic variability at the level of regions emerging during development). These examples raise the possibility of the existence of general organizational principles of biological systems, that act across levels of organization.

A bioinformatics approach has been previously proposed for the analysis of expression quantitative trait loci of functionally-related genes involved in a shared network or pathway (Pan, 2009), albeit this approach overlooks potential functional links between genes interacting only through activity regulation of their expression products (the later was proposed by Brun-Usan and Watson, 2019). Additionally, several networks/blocks/modules can interact, and an analysis of their interactions can add to our understanding of common organizational principles of living organisms. Rather than reflecting a unified graph-like network, such interactions can be better described by functionally-grouped nodes, in which the whole functional group—and not the individual elements composing it—has to be considered as the subject of interaction, and probably—the subject of modification during evolution.

To our knowledge, currently there is no work that analyzes the evolution of form and includes distant—separated by thousands million years—lineages like plants and animals, as alternatives within the “unified form landscape” of living organisms. We propose that

the striking difference observed between the evolution of the Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit and the rest of the proteome (Marchadier et al., 2016) underlies the functionally conserved “universal and versatile” “meta-bauplanning” role Ca^{2+} signaling plays across phylogenetic boundaries, in a manner independent from lineage-specific genes involved in morphogenesis. It can be expected that phenotypically similar phenomena can also take place on the basis of compounds and factors that share no kinship in different organisms. On the other hand, it is known that under particular circumstances similar components can evolve to carry out very different functions. Both these possibilities highlight the astonishing conservancy of Ca^{2+} signaling, that preserved its role as a general regulator of development in so many different biological contexts and during such an extended period of time.

The existence of cross-kingdom similarities between Ca^{2+} -regulated processes (i.e., tip growth in pollen tubes and axonal cones) may imply the existence of commonalities in the architecture and interactions between the functional blocks that give origin to Ca^{2+} signaling, as well as those executing and sensing it. As we could appreciate, in some cases particular functions are linked to specific organelles, however a function can be as well undertaken by other intracellular structures. Such replacements (like in the case of the Dynamical Patterning Modules, mentioned above) can pass inadvertent to genetic kinship-bound bioinformatics approaches and can only be identified through comparison of functions undertaken within the structural organization of the compared systems.

The examples we provided throughout the text suggest the existence of two (or three) ways in which Ca^{2+} can exert its orchestrating (=differentiating) role: 1) through Ca^{2+} transients propagating along the body of a ramified or “modular” organism (like plants [Pérez Koldenkova and Hatsugai, 2018] or cnidarians [see Jaffe, 2003]), 2) through Ca^{2+} signals that change their topology as the organism develops (animals), of which a particular example could be 3) the dynamic rearrangement of the chemotaxis-inducing Ca^{2+} gradient, observed in an aggregating *Dictyostelium* population (Lusche et al., 2012). The corresponding advantages of each orchestrating strategy are easy to discern: form establishment triggered by propagating transients supports ramified structures and allows the organism to maintain an unlimited growth of relatively independent parts, at the cost of a body shape absence. Contrary to this, an “unfolding” Ca^{2+} signaling allows achieving a relatively more intricate and reproducible structure, that inherits all the hallmarks (including —as a drawback— the deleterious ones) of the preceding developmental steps. The existence of intermediate Ca^{2+} -dependent differentiation strategies, or their combinations within a same organism, can additionally be proposed.

For future Ca^{2+} monitoring experiments, thus, it appears important to establish techniques that could allow life-long evaluation and comparison of the *absolute* levels of Ca^{2+} signaling (i.e., intensities within the same or different organisms, in terms of free Ca^{2+} concentration or CaM-mediated response) without interference induced by the indicators’

properties themselves. In this regard, the features of Ca^{2+} indicators that have not been consistently evaluated to date, but which appear to be critical for such comparative analysis, are the equal performance (dynamic range, affinity, selectivity) in different model systems, and a consistent response under normalization/calibration procedures for their readouts. Counting with the additional possibility to compare the proportion of Ca^{2+} signaling to that of other pathways (e.g., ROS; see below), may be of great advantage.

Living organisms appear to be efficient, highly reduced (if we refer to the number of constituting elements) and integrated systems, offering limited possibilities to alter their Ca^{2+} signaling. Animals, in particular, do not correspond to the most flexible realization of available Ca^{2+} signaling schemes. The proposed orchestrating role of Ca^{2+} signaling implies the requirement to know *the history* of Ca^{2+} signaling establishment in an organism, in order to understand its functioning at a particular moment in time. In this regard, we should note that the observable Ca^{2+} signaling-dependent diseases are the viable ones, the rest surely corresponding to the “Abraham Wald’s missing bullet holes” (Wald, 1943) of Ca^{2+} signaling. In animals this is probably the way (and the cost of) how morphological consistency is preserved. On the other hand, this suggests that attempts to repair such a highly-integrated and history-dependent system by approaching its constituting elements will inevitably lead to side effects (see a similar conclusion in Ugolev, 1991). Thus, an alternative way to repair (and study) such a system could be the introduction of additional Ca^{2+} signaling tools (e.g., designed Ca^{2+} -permeable channels with particular properties, and their corresponding agonists; see Hurni et al., 2017), that could add the required degree of freedom/independence and specificity to the Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit present *in-situ*. Such approach would allow addressing diseases that are non-curable within the native context of the unmodified organism. In this regard, the development of new innocuous methods of selective *in vivo* transfection looks like a task of high relevance, although an alternative approach exploiting microbiome properties has also been proposed (Tung and Levin, 2020).

Similar methods of Ca^{2+} signaling modification, although technically demanding, could be applied to morphogenesis control at the earliest stages of development. Considering existing technologies, a possible strategy to achieve localized orchestration of morphogenetic processes by Ca^{2+} could include the usage of light-(2 photon?)-activated Ca^{2+} -permeable or -releasing (Fukuda et al., 2014) tools under the control of machine learning algorithms. To this end, one of the most important technical challenges will be the possibility to step aside from traditional point-focusing elements with fixed optical properties, and their replacement by optical elements that would allow attaining complex 3/4D focused excitation *shapes* in samples, possibly through holographic techniques (Carrillo-Reid et al., 2019; Marshel et al., 2019), stretchable optics, or elements with tunable optical properties (Berto et al., 2019). Achieving this goal could also take advantage of synthetic gene circuits (e.g., Bashor et al., 2019) for localized expression of

either natural or engineered elements of the Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit at particular locations within the developing living system. Similar strategies can be applied to achieve optical “triggering” and workload adaptation of the already developed structure (to establish the orchestration-to-triggering coupling).

An arising feature of Ca^{2+} signaling that could interfere with all these attempts, is the importance Ca^{2+} transporters have as *direct interaction partners*, and not only as Ca^{2+} flux mediators with particular properties: the very presence of such elements of the Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit appears to be important, providing an additional, heretofore unexplored way in which Ca^{2+} signaling can be related to physiological outcomes and through which specificity can be added to faceless Ca^{2+} transients. Taking together the presented results, it appears that this feature is modified during development: at early stages, the source of Ca^{2+} transients seems irrelevant, being the Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit established in a genetically-defined way, while later differentiation is accompanied by selection of particular Ca^{2+} sources, in accordance with the internal and external cues resulting from the organism functioning in its environment, and at this, or later stage, Ca^{2+} transporters also become important as interaction partners. Several studies refer to this last property of Ca^{2+} signaling (for IP_3Rs — Bartok et al., 2019, for TRPs — Ferreira and Vermot, 2017; Canales et al., 2019, for STIM1 and Orai1 — Humeau et al., 2017; Latour et al., 2018; probably it also applies to DEK1 channels in plants, Landrein and Ingram, 2019).

In this work we presented mostly positive evidence supporting the claims we propose. We are aware of a lack of sufficient negative evidence: analyses of cases when the proposed mechanisms are not supported, or proofs that other mechanisms are not part of the “core machinery” involved in the identified programs and functional blocks.

Some other important issues were not covered in the present work. For instance:

- We were primarily interested in general Ca^{2+} -related processes involved in form establishment, and thus, analyses of several particular and specialized Ca^{2+} -dependent phenomena was largely skipped. Examples of such phenomena are, among other: nuclear Ca^{2+} signaling, Ca^{2+} -related diseases, senescence-associated changes in Ca^{2+} signaling, autophagy, fertilization, excitability, plasticity, circadian clock, and Ca^{2+} -dependent secretion. In addition, we only marginally approached Ca^{2+} relay mechanisms (Marchadier et al., 2016).

- In many cases, pH changes are also observed in association with Ca^{2+} , not only in acidic Ca^{2+} stores (see about their importance in Gross, 2009; Salerno et al., 2014), but also in the cytosol and the extracellular space (e.g., in tumor microenvironments). These pH changes may carry standalone signaling importance and/or modulate the Ca^{2+} signaling capacity to regulate morphogenesis and regeneration (Covi and Hand, 2007; Adams et al., 2007; Ko et al., 2020; Molinari and Nervo, 2020).

- Ca^{2+} is not the only ion relevant for the processes we analyzed above; other ions (and concomitant membrane potential changes) may also be involved and modulate the Ca^{2+} -evoked responses (e.g., see Lusche et al., 2012; Kischel et al., 2019). Similarly, we did not approach the relationship between Ca^{2+} signaling and electric fields in detail.

- Ca^{2+} signaling is intricately interleaved with reactive oxygen species (ROS) signaling in living organisms. Given the differences existing between animals and plants in regard to Ca^{2+} signaling, we can expect similar or higher differences to exist at the level of the coupled Ca^{2+} -ROS signaling between these two lineages, particularly during the orchestration-to-triggering role transition. We presented a preliminary analysis of this coupling in a previous work, for the particular case of plants (Pérez Koldenkova and Hatsugai, 2018).

Contributions

Conceived the study — VPK; added the magic — GYL; apported and fact-checked molecular biology data — YP; apported and fact-checked zoology and botany data — AVC; apported and fact-checked general theoretical biological concepts — GYL; apported and fact-checked data on Ca^{2+} signaling — VPK. All authors read, improved and approved the final manuscript text and figures.

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Conflicts of interest

Nothing to declare

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Figure captions

Fig 1. Composition of the functional blocks identified in the present work, a schematic representation.

The existence of two major functional blocks is proposed in the present work: migration-chemotaxis (blue) and proliferation-quiescence-based (yellow). Organelles involved in each functional block are schematically represented and enclosed. Some organelles (e.g., the ER) may have roles in both functional blocks.

Fig 2. Comparison of the current and proposed paradigms of Ca^{2+} signaling.

A. Role of Ca^{2+} signaling according to the current paradigm of genotype-into-phenotype conversion. **B.** Proposed extended role of Ca^{2+} signaling, containing a self-regulatory feedback loop.

Fig 3. Cell migration types and transitions between them.

Three parameters influence the migration type: adhesion, contractility and confinement. Confinement of mesenchymal cells induces their rounding, and the appearance of blebs. Such cells can spontaneously start migrating using either of the amoeboid migration types (A1 or A2), or both, in different proportions. Amoeboid migration is considered more ancient than mesenchymal migration. Schematic representation as proposed by Liu et al., (2015), with modifications. Details in the text.

Fig 4. Place of Ca^{2+} signaling in the structure of cell cycle regulation in animals and plants.

In animal cells, activation of proliferation is mediated by Ca^{2+} -dependent expression of cell cycle regulators — cyclins and cyclin-dependent kinases (CYC/CDKs). In plant cells, Ca^{2+} plays rather a modulatory/permissive role, modulating the activity of these proteins. Proliferation progression or arrest in plant cells depends on proteins, the activity of which is modulated in a Ca^{2+} -dependent manner. Details in the text.

Fig 5. Proposed modifications to the Ca^{2+} signaling during development (in the case of animals).

From left to right — an organism at different stages of development (earlier at left, later at right). Stages of differentiation are indicated with dotted lines (from top — less differentiated stage, to bottom — more differentiated stage; the direction of differentiation is indicated by black arrows). Each bifurcation corresponds to a progression toward a subsequent differentiation stage. Bifurcations coincide with cells' divisions at initial stages of development, but at later stages they correspond to rearrangements of the Ca^{2+} signaling toolkit; they also correspond to critical phases. Different tissues are characterized by different degrees of differentiation depth (different distances from the top). Red arrows

indicate the two roles of Ca^{2+} signaling: orchestrating (curved arrows) and triggering (straight arrows). At the “front” of differentiation, Ca^{2+} signaling orchestrates this process by providing the feedback from external cues (=internalizing them). In differentiated tissues, the triggering (“definitive function”) role of Ca^{2+} signaling is more evident. This is a simplified scheme, not including dedifferentiation and regeneration.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

A. Current paradigm

B. Required paradigm

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

